

Inherit

Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services/D2.3

WP 2, T 2.4

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Table of contents

Table of contents	4
Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	7
Executive Summary	8
1. Introduction.....	9
1.1 Objectives of the Deliverable	9
1.2 Overview of INHERIT Services and Pilot Implementation	10
1.3 Structure of the Deliverable	13
2. Methodology.....	15
2.1 Underlying Definitions	16
2.1.1. User Stories	16
2.1.2. User Requirements	16
2.1.3. Use Cases	17
3. Phase A: Identification of User Stories & User Requirements	18
3.1 User Stories	18
3.2 Service Descriptions.....	23
3.2.1 User Requirements	23
3.3 Workshop – 1° Round of the Co-creation Activities.....	26
3.3.1 Workshop Implementation and Participation	26
3.3.2 Structure of the 1st Co-creation Workshop	27
3.3.3 Feedback received from the 1st Co-creation Workshop.....	28
4 Phase B: Co-creating Use-friendly Environments	35
4.1 User-flow Diagrams.....	35
4.2 Workshop – 2nd Round of the Co-creation Activities	35
4.2.1 Workshop Implementation and Participation	35
4.2.2 Structure of the 2nd Co-creation Workshop	35
4.2.3 Feedback received from the 2nd Co-creation Workshop	36
5 Phase C: Services Demonstrations and Final Refinements	38
5.1 Development of Services Demos	38
5.2 Workshop – 3rd Round of the Co-creation Activities.....	38
5.2.1 Workshop Implementation and Participation	38
5.2.2 Structure of the 3rd Co-creation Workshop.....	39
5.2.3 Feedback received from the 3rd Co-creation Workshop	40
Conclusions	42

References 43

Annex A 44

Pilot 1 - City Administration Headquarters, Croatia	44
Pilot 3 - ELLET Building under Acropolis, Greece	49
Pilot 4 – Concert Hall, Latvia	53
Pilot 5 - Social Residential Building, Poland	55
Pilot 6 - Monastery “Ntra. Sra. Del Prado”, Spain	57
Pilot 7 - City of Visby, UNESCO World Heritage Site, Sweden	59
Pilot 8 - Ahmet Pristina City Archive & Museum (APIKAM), Turkiye	62

Annex B 65

s.1 Interactive screen usage and AR-VR interfaces	65
s.2 Modelling & simulation environment	66
s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	67
s.4 IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation	69
s.5 Energy forecasting and intelligent management	72
s.6 Digital Twin for Heritage facilities’ real time monitoring operation & management	73
s.7 Real-time insights on activity and mobility partners	78
s.8 Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	80
s.9 GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	81
s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	83

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of the INHERIT Services.....	11
Table 2: Summary of the INHERIT pilots and key characteristics	12
Table 3: Mapping of the INHERIT solution across the eight pilot sites	13
Table 4: Breakdown of the deliverable sections.....	14
Table 5: User Story (US) template.....	19
Table 6: Overview of the User Stories per Pilot.....	20
Table 7: Mapping of User Stories by pilot site and stakeholder prioritisation	22
Table 8: Service Description template	23
Table 9: Consolidated User Requirements	25
Table 10: URs categorisation per service and MoSCoW prioritization.....	33
Table 11: Key results from the 2nd co-creation workshop of the INHERIT services	37
Table 12: Multi-Dimensional Validation of INHERIT Services: Perception, Value, and Technical Feedback	41

List of Figures

Figure 1: Three-phase methodology for the co-creation of the INHERIT services.....	15
Figure 2: Mapping User Requirements to INHERIT Services	26
Figure 3: Screenshot from the 1st co-creation workshop of the INHERIT services.....	27

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Figure 4: Screenshot from the break-out rooms during the 1st co-creation workshop of the INHERIT services.....	28
Figure 5: Example of the first co-creation activity of the 2nd Workshop	36
Figure 6: Example of the second co-creation activity of the 2nd Workshop	36
Figure 7: Screenshot from the 3rd co-creation workshop of the INHERIT services	38
Figure 8: Screenshot from the third activity of the 3rd co-creation workshop.....	40

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR/VR	Augmented Reality / Virtual Reality
CH	Cultural Heritage
D	Deliverable
DSS	Decision Support Services
GA	Grant Agreement
GIS	Geographic Information System
H-BIM	Heritage Building Information Modelling
IBB	Izmir Metropolitan Municipality
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
IoT	Internet of Things
MoSCoW	Must have, Should have, Could have, Won't have
MSF	Multi-Stakeholder Forum
NEB	New European Bauhaus
RES	Renewable Energy Source
s	Service
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Analysis/Assessment
T	Task
UC	Use Case
UR	User Requirement
US	User Story
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable consolidates the methodology used for the co-creation of the **INHERIT Decision Support Services (DSS)** and fulfils the objectives of **Deliverable D2.3 “Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services”**. Building on the outcomes of the stakeholder mapping and engagement activities reported in **D2.1 “Social Labs Methodological Handbook, high-level requirements”** and **D2.2 “Active societal participation & enabling conditions for the INHERIT heritage-built environment”**, the document describes the methodological steps followed from the identification of user needs and User Stories (USs) to the evaluation of the services.

The co-creation process was structured across three iterative phases, bridging the gap between technical service providers and the diverse needs of the Cultural Heritage (CH) sector. Key outcomes of this consolidation include:

- **User-Centric Foundation:** The derivation of **34 User Stories** across 7 European pilot sites, ensuring that the 11 INHERIT services are grounded in real-world scenarios.
- **Technical Traceability:** The extraction and internal validation of **74 User Requirements (URs)**. These are prioritised using the **MoSCoW method** (Must, Should, Could, Won't have) to guide the final development stages.
- **Stakeholder Validation:** The results of three thematic workshops involving experts, facility managers, and local authorities are reviewed. These sessions allowed for the "User Value Mapping" and "Perception Tracking" of service demos, ensuring the tools are intuitive and relevant to their professional contexts.

By linking specific user needs to technical functionalities, D2.3 provides a clear roadmap for the final refinement of the INHERIT services. It serves as a verification document that ensures the technical output of the project remains aligned with the needs of architects, residents, and policy makers, ultimately fostering more sustainable and resilient heritage-built environments.

1. Introduction

The INHERIT project focuses on the development of advanced solutions to support the sustainable, inclusive, and resource-efficient transformation of CH buildings. The project adopts a comprehensive approach that combines a structured methodological framework with the use of advanced Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), including the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and data-driven analytics, alongside relevant social and behavioural practices.

Given the strong social dimension of the project and the active involvement of stakeholders, co-creation is essential in developing the INHERIT services. This process ensures the integration of valuable social and technological inputs, aligns the services with end-user needs, and enhances their long-term adoption and sustainability beyond the project lifetime. INHERIT encompasses the implementation of 11 services, to be piloted across 8 CH sites throughout Europe.

Section 1 includes the objectives of this deliverable, an overview of the INHERIT services, a brief description of the pilot sites, and the structure of the document.

1.1 Objectives of the Deliverable

The consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services (D2.3) represent a pivotal milestone in the project's development. Originating from WP2 (Stakeholder Engagement, Co-creation & Social Innovation) and specifically T2.4 (Co-creating the INHERIT solutions and use scenarios), these factors bridge the gap between theoretical methodology and practical application.

The goal of WP2 is to **embed social innovation** within the INHERIT framework. By identifying stakeholder interests and evaluating the impact of project activities, WP2 ensures that all outcomes are socially grounded and supported by proven engagement strategies. Building on the social foundation established in WP2 overall, Task 2.4 specifically focuses on the **co-creation of solutions and use scenarios**. This ensures that the resulting services are shaped by stakeholder perspectives and provide practical value tailored to their specific needs.

To achieve this, Deliverable 2.3 aims to:

- present the **three-phase co-design methodology** applied,
- outline the identified **user stories** and corresponding **user requirements**,
- summarise the feedback collected from the **co-creation workshops** throughout the three phases.

As a core component of the INHERIT project, this deliverable marks the starting point of the service development process. It begins with a comprehensive assessment of **user needs and expectations** (Phase 1). These insights are subsequently translated into **user requirements** and technical specifications, forming the foundation for the development of **user flows** (Phase 2). In the final

phase (Phase 3), the service providers further refine these flows and integrate them into the **service demonstrations**.

1.2 Overview of INHERIT Services and Pilot Implementation

To address the multifaceted challenges of the heritage-built environment, INHERIT is developing 11 innovative solutions designed to enhance sustainability, accessibility, and resilience. These services are strategically categorized into **three thematic pillars** based on their specific focus within the building life cycle:

1. **Design and Renovation**
2. **Monitoring, Operation, and Management**
3. **Preservation and Maintenance**

These 11 services will be demonstrated and validated across 8 diverse pilot sites throughout Europe. This variety of locations, ranging from landmark buildings to historic city quarters, enables the project to test the scalability and impact of the INHERIT solutions in different socioeconomic and cultural contexts.

A brief overview of these services and pilot sites is provided below, followed by detailed descriptions in the subsequent sections.

Thematic Pillars	INHERIT Innovative Solutions	Description
Data Exchange	s.0 Heritage buildings smartification & data exchange	The components include sensors and monitoring systems for the collection and exchange of data related to the condition and performance of heritage buildings, building on existing initiatives in the area of Data Spaces.
Design and Renovation	s.1 Interactive screen use and AR-VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction	The AR/VR service uses AR for on-the-job training and VR for pre-intervention planning in CH buildings. It helps reduce costs, detect errors early, engages stakeholders, and allows users to familiarise themselves with sites before work begins, enhancing understanding and overall experience.
	s.2 Modelling and simulation environment	The service uses the DREEM model from TEESlab, to analyse energy performance in INHERIT pilot buildings. It allows users to assess consumption, explore renovation savings, and apply techno-economic assessments to prioritize actions, providing a holistic renovation plan with options and visualized results.
	s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	The service provides decision support for optimal renovation planning of historic buildings using explicit multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) to balance heritage preservation with economic, environmental, and societal factors.
Monitoring, Operation	s.4 IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation	The IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation monitors comfort factors, temperature, lighting, noise, and air quality, in historic buildings and suggests data-driven improvements. It identifies

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Thematic Pillars	INHERIT Innovative Solutions	Description
		issues, recommends changes in building use or management, and incorporates user feedback to enhance well-being, safety, and energy efficiency.
	s.5 Energy forecasting and intelligent management	This service improves energy management in CH buildings by using advanced forecasting models, including machine learning and Transfer Learning, to predict energy use and indoor conditions. It provides data-driven recommendations for load shifting, peak smoothing, and optimal use of renewable energy and storage.
	s.6 Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring and management	The Digital Twin service creates a virtual replica of a cultural heritage site, combining BIM-based static data, real-time sensor data, and performance models. It enables historical and real-time visualization, data analysis, scenario simulation, and alert generation.
	s.7 Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	The service gives real-time data and analytics on visitor activity and mobility, providing insights into behaviour and crowd flow. It helps management optimize experiences, allocate resources, and make data-driven operational decisions.
Preservation and Maintenance	s.8 Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	The Preventive maintenance service is a multidimensional H-BIM model that integrates inspection data to simulate interventions, supporting sustainable, efficient, and cost-effective preventive maintenance of heritage buildings.
	s.9 GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	The GIS-based solution service helps heritage professionals plan maintenance for CH buildings using a GIS-based map with building details and image processing to group similar buildings, enabling targeted identification of maintenance needs.
	s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	The service assesses climate change risks for building stock by modelling exposure, vulnerability, and hazard probability. It evaluates energy demand under different scenarios and calculates KPIs to compare the impact of key climate hazards on CH buildings.

Table 1: Overview of the INHERIT Services

Pilot Sites	Characteristics
Pilot 1 – City Administration Headquarters, City of Jastrebarsko, Croatia	The pilot site is the City Administration Headquarters of Jastrebarsko, a protected cultural heritage building constructed in a late 19th–early 20th century classical style, featuring articulated profiles and ornamental elements on the main façade.

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Pilot 2 – “La Cité du goût”, City of Noisiel, France	The new site in Noisiel, near Paris, is part of a former industrial complex being transformed into housing, co-living spaces, a hotel, and cultural areas called “La Cité du goût.” Several buildings are historic monuments. The project aims to create an exceptional living environment, promote social and intergenerational interaction, and protect biodiversity with green spaces.
Pilot 3 - ELLET Building under Acropolis, City of Athens, Greece	The ELLET building is located on Tripodon Street, directly beneath the Acropolis, an area of significant historical and cultural importance. Built in the early 19th century, the two-storey building hosts seminars, conferences, events, and displays of historical artefacts on the ground floor, while the headquarters’ offices are located on the upper floor.
Pilot 4 – Concert Hall, City of Riga, Latvia	The Ave Sol Concert Hall is in the historical centre of Riga and was originally constructed between 1780 and 1785 as the St. Peter and Pavel Church. The building underwent restoration and reconstruction between 1980 and 1987 and was subsequently repurposed as a concert hall.
Pilot 5 – Social Residential Building, City of Gdynia, Poland	The pilot building was constructed in 1928, prior to the second World War, and is owned by the City of Gdynia. It functions as a social residential building and is listed in the Municipal Register of Monuments under the supervision of the Municipal Cultural Heritage Conservator.
Pilot 6 – Monastery “Ntra. Sra. Del Prado”, Castile and Leon, Spain	The monastery, near the Pisuega River and the Parliament of Castile and León, was declared a national historical monument in 1877. It has three two-story cloisters with semicircular arches and was restored in the 1980s and later converted into offices for the Castilla y León Regional Government.
Pilot 7 – City of Visby, UNESCO World Heritage Site, City of Visby, Sweden	Visby’s historic district, a UNESCO World Heritage Site, is a well-preserved northern European medieval walled trading town with high-quality historic buildings still in active use. On Gotland, the island where Visby is located, smart and renewable energy systems are being piloted.
Pilot 8 - Ahmet Pristina City Archive & Museum (APİKAM), City of İzmir, Turkiye	The building has high historical significance as the first fire station built by the İzmir Metropolitan Municipality after the Great İzmir Fire of 1922. It currently hosts cultural, research, and administrative functions, with public spaces, offices, and meeting areas distributed across three floors and a courtyard.

Table 2: Summary of the INHERIT pilots and key characteristics

[Pilot 2 was revised following the Grant Agreement amendment. As Workshops 1 and 2 were conducted prior to this change, no stakeholder input is included for the updated pilot in this deliverable.]

To ensure a robust validation of the INHERIT methodology, services are strategically distributed across eight diverse pilot sites, as shown in Table 3. Notably, **s.0, the project’s core Data Exchange Platform, is deployed universally**. This widespread implementation is fundamental to the project's architecture, as s.0 serves as the primary gateway for **receiving and managing data** from all other services.

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

s.0 Heritage buildings smartification & data exchange								
Design and Renovation								
s.1 Interactive screen use and AR-VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction								
s.2 Modelling and simulation environment								
s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning								
Monitoring, Operation, and Management								
s.4 IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation								
s.5 Energy forecasting and intelligent management								
s.6 Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring and management								
s.7 Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns								
Preservation and Maintenance								
s.8 Preventive maintenance with H-BIM								
s.9 GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance								
s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios								

Table 3: Mapping of the INHERIT solution across the eight pilot sites

1.3 Structure of the Deliverable

To provide a clear and logical progression of the work performed, this deliverable is structured to reflect the evolution from initial stakeholder engagement to the final technical validation of the services. Following this introductory chapter, the document is organized into five main sections that detail the transition from methodology and user needs to the technical design and demonstration of the INHERIT services.

The following Table 4 provides an overview of the document's structure and the specific topics covered in each section:

Section	Topic	Description
Section 2	Methodology	Outlines the overarching co-creation framework and the multi-phase approach used to engage stakeholders across the pilot sites.
Section 3	Phase A: Identification of User Stories & User Requirements	Details the extraction of 34 User Stories and their translation into 74 prioritized Functional and Non-Functional Requirements.
Section 4	Phase B: Co-creating User-friendly Environments	Reports on the second workshop phase, focusing on user flow validation, UI/UX feedback, and the initial shaping of service interfaces.
Section 5	Phase C: Services Demonstrations and Final Refinements	Documents the validation of functional service demos and the collection of final stakeholder insights to guide the last development wave.
Section 6	Conclusion	Summarizes the consolidation factors and establishes the roadmap for the final implementation of the INHERIT services.

Table 4: Breakdown of the deliverable sections

2. Methodology

To ensure that the INHERIT services are both **impactful and user-centric**, the project engages a broad spectrum of stakeholders. This includes those who design and implement heritage interventions, such as **architects and engineers**, as well as the **residents and owners** who interact with these spaces daily. Furthermore, the process involves **researchers, academics, and official authorities, such as ministries of energy and culture**, to ensure alignment with policy and regulation. This collaboration is fundamental to aligning technical development with real-world expectations and practical requirements.

The co-creation of the INHERIT services follows a **three-phase methodology** (Figure 1) designed to align stakeholder insight with technical execution. Each phase ensures that the final tools are both operationally effective and deeply rooted in the needs of those who will use them.

Figure 1: Three-phase methodology for the co-creation of the INHERIT services

- **Phase A: Identification of User Stories & User Requirements (M4 – M12)**

This initial phase focuses on introducing the proposed services to stakeholders to gather feedback on their specific requirements. The goal is to **understand the unique challenges of each pilot site**, ensuring that future services are effectively integrated into the heritage-built environment. The **feedback collected informs the specific features and designs** that will be developed in the next phase.

- **Phase B: Co-creating the front-end of the INHERIT services (M13 – M22)**

Starting in M13, this phase focuses on the **design of intuitive environments and user flow diagrams**. An online workshop is organised to share these flows and early service versions, allowing stakeholders to provide direct input on the user experience. This ensures the services are user-friendly and closely aligned with the practical workflows of the end users. The refined user flows produced in this phase serve as the blueprint for the functional demonstration versions developed for the final stage.

- **Phase C: Validation and final iteration (M23 – M29)**

In the final phase, **demonstration versions of the services** are made available for stakeholder review. Through collaborative workshops, the "second wave" of INHERIT services is evaluated for usability, clarity, and overall comprehension. This feedback initiates the final iteration process to polish the services for their final application.

This **three-phase structure creates an ongoing feedback loop** between technical developers and project stakeholders. By structuring the process in this way, the methodology systematically incorporates user insights at every stage, from identifying site-specific needs to refining service demonstrations. This collaborative approach ensures that the resulting INHERIT services are practical, user-friendly, and tailored to the unique requirements of the heritage-built environment.

More detailed descriptions of each phase are included in the next sections of this deliverable.

2.1 Underlying Definitions

To ensure consistency and a clear understanding of the core concepts used throughout the INHERIT project and this deliverable, this section provides definitions of key elements, including user stories, user requirements, and use cases.

2.1.1. User Stories

A user story (US) is a short, simple description of a feature or functionality from the perspective of an end-user or stakeholder. It captures what the user wants to achieve, why it is important, and the value it delivers. User stories are typically written in plain language to ensure a shared understanding among stakeholders, developers, and designers, and they serve as the basis for defining requirements, prioritizing features, and guiding development (Cohn, 2004; Schwaber & Beedle, 2002; Leffingwell, 2011).

2.1.2. User Requirements

A user requirement (UR) is a detailed statement of a need or expectation that a system, service, or product must fulfill from the perspective of the end-user or stakeholder. User requirements describe what the system should do or what qualities it should have, focusing on functionality, usability, and constraints relevant to the users' goals (Cohn, 2004; Leffingwell, 2011). They are typically derived from user stories, and stakeholder engagement and serve as the foundation for technical specifications, design decisions, and testing.

2.1.3. Use Cases

A use case (UC) is a structured description of how a user interacts with a system or service to achieve a specific goal. It captures the sequence of steps, conditions, and interactions required to complete a task, providing a clear understanding of system functionality from the user's perspective (Cockburn, 2001; Leffingwell, 2011). Use cases are commonly used to translate user requirements into actionable design and development tasks, and they support validation, testing, and communication among stakeholders.

3. Phase A: Identification of User Stories & User Requirements

The first phase of the co-creation approach lays the foundation of the development of the INHERIT solution by **identifying the user needs and defining early functional expectations**.

Based on the **stakeholder personas** that have already been identified under T2.1 Engagement strategy for participatory and co-creation processes and reported in D2.1 Social Labs Methodological Handbook, high-level requirements, **the pilot leaders developed a number of user stories** to identify the needs.

To this end, a structured process was followed, encompassing the identification of user stories and use scenarios, their mapping to the end users and stakeholders previously identified by each pilot leader, the collection of service descriptions from the service providers, and their subsequent translation into user requirements. The following sections provide a detailed overview of each of these elements, including the relevant tables and inputs from pilots and service providers.

3.1 User Stories

Although referred to as “user stories”, the template integrates use-scenario elements in order to contextualise user needs within real pilot operations. Each user story acts as an entry point, while the associated description, needs, barriers, and technical resources describe the corresponding use scenario.

These user stories provide a structured way to translate co-creation outcomes into actionable inputs for service design and development. Pilots proceeded with filling out user stories, at least one per service featured in each pilot, by providing the accompanying information outlined in the template below.

User Story ID	US [X.Y]
User Story Title	[title of your User Story]
Pilot	[which pilot relates to this user story]
Relevant Service(s)	[services that are related to the user story]
Description	[describe how this service will help your pilot execute the desired results]
Needs	[describe what are the needs addressed in the given scenario] <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Installation of sensors and monitoring system 2. Collecting and analysing the data collected
Potential Barriers	[describe potential barriers or challenges associated with the service]

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Equipment	[describe any relevant equipment that could be leveraged by the service]				
	Equipment	Short description			
	Equipment Name 1				
	Equipment Name 2				
	Equipment Name 3				
Datasets	[describe any relevant existing dataset that could be leveraged by the service; specify the formats, size, means of access]				
	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Name 1				
	Dataset Name 2				
	Dataset Name 3				
	Dataset Name 4				
	Dataset Name 5				

Table 5: User Story (US) template

The following Table 6 outlines the USs identified by each pilot. These stories are derived directly from the specific services relevant to each pilot, as identified in Table 3. For a deeper dive into the details and context of each story, please refer to the comprehensive information in Annex A.

Pilot	U.S No	U.S Title
Pilot 1	US 1.1	Sensors and monitoring system
	US 1.2	Optimal renovation strategies
	US 1.3	Measured and quantified thermal comfort and air quality
	US 1.4	Energy performance analysis
	US 1.5	KPIs impacted by different climate scenarios
Pilot 2	<i>No available USs for the new pilot</i>	
Pilot 3	US 3.1	Operational recommendations for noise comfort and air quality
	US 3.2	Energy performance analysis
	US 3.3	Operational recommendations for crowd and mobility management
	US 3.4	Optimal renovation planning proposals based on energy performance data
Pilot 4	US 4.1	Visualization of energy performance of the building
	US 4.2	Renovation action plan
	US 4.3	Regulated indoor air quality

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Pilot	U.S No	U.S Title
	US 4.4	Clustered with other CH buildings
Pilot 5	US 5.1	Sensor and monitoring system for building maintenance
	US 5.2	Selection of the optimal renovation scenario based on energy performance data and AR/VR interface
Pilot 6	US 6.1	Checking the feasibility of preventive conservation and proper maintenance of CH buildings with HBIM and its cost-effective energy performance optimisation.
	US 6.2	Recommendation on Historic Urban Landscape for cost-effective and less disruptive modernisation and preservation of the CH building
Pilot 7	US 7.1	Modelling and simulation environment
	US 7.2	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management
	US 7.3	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance
	US 7.4	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios
Pilot 8	US 8.1	Assessing impacts of different climate scenarios
	US 8.2	Collecting data related to energy performance
	US 8.3	Assessment of optimal renovation approaches
	US 8.4	Enhancement of crowd and mobility management
	US 8.5	Assessing impacts of different climate scenarios

Table 6: Overview of the User Stories per Pilot

The following Table 7 presents a mapping of the User Stories categorized by stakeholder and pilot. Beyond simply listing participants, the table illustrates the prioritization of stakeholders for each specific story, categorized by High, Medium, and Low importance.

	US ID	US Title	End User / Stakeholders		
			High importance	Medium importance	Low importance
Pilot 1	US 1.1	Sensors and monitoring system	Faculty of Civil Engineering at University of Zagreb	Administrative Department for Spatial Planning, Construction and Environmental Protection	Public Institution Green Ring of Zagreb County
	US 1.2	Optimal renovation strategies	Administrative Department for Spatial Planning, Construction and Environmental Protection	Community of Cultural Associations of City of Jastrebarsko	City of Jastrebarsko

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	US ID	US Title	End User / Stakeholders		
			High importance	Medium importance	Low importance
	US 1.3	Measured and quantified thermal comfort and air quality	Public Institution Green Ring of Zagreb County	Faculty of Civil Engineering at University of Zagreb	Croatian Forest Research Institute
	US 1.4	Energy performance analysis	Faculty of Civil Engineering at University of Zagreb	Public Institution Green Ring of Zagreb County	Administrative Department for Spatial Planning, Construction and Environmental Protection City of Jastrebarsko
	US 1.5	KPIs impacted by different climate scenarios	Conservation Department of Ministry for Culture and Media for the Area of Zagreb County	Administrative Department for Culture, Sport, Technical Culture and Civil Society of Zagreb County	
Pilot 2			Not available for the new pilot		
Pilot 3	US 3.1	Operational recommendations for noise comfort and air quality	Municipality of Athens – Deputy Mayor of Athens	Architectural Council of Licensing	Committee of Plaka Residents' Initiative
	US 3.2	Energy performance analysis	NEB committee – Ministry of Energy	Students, researchers (National Technical University of Athens)	Engineers (volunteers)
	US 3.3	Operational recommendations for crowd and mobility management	Technical Chamber of Greece	Greek Association of Architects	Students and researchers (National Technical University of Athens)
	US 3.4	Optimal renovation planning proposals based on energy performance data	Architectural Council for Licensing	Greek Historic Houses Project	Local Association of Athens
Pilot 4	US 4.1	Visualisation of energy performance of the building	Riga Energy Agency	Technology provider	Riga Technical University
	US 4.2	Renovation action plan	Riga City Council (Construction Authority)	Disabled people (NGO Sustento)	Riga City Council (Financial department)
	US 4.3	Regulated indoor air quality	Riga City Council (Construction Authority)	Riga Technical University	Financial Institution (Latvian Environmental Investment Fund)
	US 4.4	Clustered with other CH buildings	Riga City Council (Property Department)	AVE SOL building users - choirs	National Cultural Heritage Administration

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	US ID	US Title	End User / Stakeholders		
			High importance	Medium importance	Low importance
Pilot 5	US 5.1	Sensor and monitoring system for building maintenance	3L Architekten	Department of Regional and Spatial Development	Energy department of city of Gdynia
	US 5.2	Selection of the optimal renovation scenario based on energy performance data and AR/VR interface	Energy Department of City of Gdynia	Pich architects	Mostostal Warszawa S.A. - Construction
Pilot 6	US 6.1	Checking the feasibility of preventive conservation and proper maintenance of CH buildings with H-BIM and its cost-effective energy performance optimisation.	Direccion General de Patrimonio Cultural. Consejeria de Cultura; Turismo y Deporte. JCYL	Consejeria de Cultura, Turismo y Deporte. JCYL	AEICE
	US 6.2	Recommendation on Historic Urban Landscape for cost-effective and less disruptive modernisation and preservation of the CH building	Consejeria de Cultura, Turismo y Deporte. JCYL	Direccion General de Patrimonio Cultural. Consejeria de Cultura; Turismo y Deporte. JCYL	AEICE
Pilot 7	US 7.1	Modelling and simulation environment	Byggnadsvårds företagen	Riksantikvarie ämbetet	Byggnadsvårdsföretagen
	US 7.2	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	Energicentrum Gotland	Riksantikvarie ämbetet	House owners in Visby/ Fastighetsägarna Gotland
	US 7.3	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	Byggnadsvårds företagen	House owners in Visby/ Fastighetsägarna Gotland	Riksantikvarie ämbetet
	US 7.4	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	Visby innerstadsförening	Världsarv srådet	House owners in Visby/ fastighetsägarna Gotland
Pilot 8	US 8.1	Assessing impacts of different climate scenarios	Academic Scholars using the Archive Building	Yaşar University, Izmir, Türkiye	Izmir National Library Foundation
	US 8.2	Collecting data related to energy performance		Izmir Institute of Technology, Izmir, Türkiye	Izmir National Library Foundation
	US 8.3	Assessment of optimal renovation approaches	Department of City Planning Supervision	Constructor	Izmir first Conservation Council of Cultural Heritage

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	US ID	US Title	End User / Stakeholders		
			High importance	Medium importance	Low importance
	US 8.4	Enhancement of crowd and mobility management	Izmir Institute of Technology, Izmir, Türkiye	Izmir first Conservation Council of Cultural Heritage	Directorate of City Archive, Museums and Libraries
	US 8.5	Assessing impacts of different climate scenarios	Academic Scholars using the Archive Building	Yaşar University, Izmir, Türkiye	Izmir National library foundation

Table 7: Mapping of User Stories by pilot site and stakeholder prioritisation

3.2 Service Descriptions

To complement the user-oriented perspectives, the service providers have developed detailed descriptions of the INHERIT services based on their initial service concepts. Using the standardised template presented in Table 8, service providers have formalised their original ideas into a structured format that defines the scope and technical direction of each solution. These descriptions serve as the technical foundation for the development phase, ensuring that all services are aligned with the project's overall objectives.

A comprehensive breakdown of these detailed descriptions, including the specific functionalities of each service, is provided in Annex B.

Service ID					
Service name	[title of your Service]				
Lead Partner	[which partner leads the service]				
General Description					
General Description	[general Description of the tool; explain the motivation, goal and context of its use]				
Service Functionalities					
Input Data	[describe the input data requested by the service; Specify how this will be collected (open/pilot data etc.)]				
	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Name 1				
	Dataset Name 2				
	Dataset Name 3				
Output Data	[describe the output of the service and how the user is expected to interact with it]				
Service Workflow	[describe a sequence of steps to explain the inner logic of the service]				

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Internal architecture & Technologies used	[explain the functionality of the service, explain the subcomponents and the inner architecture of the service, and which technologies are used. Is the tool containerized (e.g., available as Docker image)?]
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Table 8: Service Description template

3.2.1 User Requirements

Following the formalization of these service descriptions, a set of user requirements was extracted internally by the project team. These requirements translate the technical capabilities of the services into specific user-focused needs and functionalities. This internal extraction served as a critical output, directly shaping the first phase of the co-creation process.

The table below (Table 9) presents the finalised set of user requirements, which is the result of the entire co-creation process. This consolidated version integrates the initial internal requirements with direct feedback and insights gathered from end-users and stakeholders during the Phase 1 workshops.

In addition to listing the requirements, the table shows the direct link between each user requirement and the corresponding INHERIT services. It also identifies the type of requirement—categorizing them as either **functional** or **non-functional**.

UR (ID)	Related Service (ID)	Functional/ Non-Functional	Brief Description
UR01	s.0, s.4, s.5	Functional	The system should efficiently gather and frequently update data from sensors and smart meters
UR02	s.2, s.3, s.9	Non-functional	The system should efficiently gather data related to energy consumption
UR03	s.4, s.9	Functional	The system should relate energy consumption and air quality data with the comfort level
UR04	s.3, s.5	Functional	The system should compile a list of optimal renovation plans
UR05	s.3, s.5	Functional	INHERIT should assess the renovation plans, as well as their impact, and propose the optimal in terms of financial and energy savings
UR06	s.4	Functional	The system should provide actionable suggestions for optimizing energy usage and indoor comfort, tailored to the use of building
UR07	s.5, s.7	Functional	The system should analyze data related to energy consumption (including historical energy usage, current consumption levels, renewable energy resources, etc.) and provide detailed insights into energy consumption trends

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

UR (ID)	Related Service (ID)	Functional/ Non-Functional	Brief Description
			(e.g. peak demand periods and inefficiencies) to facilitate informed decision-making.
UR08	s.2, s.6, s.8	Functional	The system should analyze energy consumption patterns and provide strategies to optimize energy usage and minimize costs.
UR09	s.0, s.10	Functional	INHERIT should be able to simulate various climate hazard scenarios, such as extreme temperatures, storms, floods or droughts
UR10	s.0, s.10	Functional	Through the calculation of relevant KPIs, INHERIT should assess the impact of the climate hazards both at city and at building scale
UR11	s.4	Functional	Evaluate noise levels both outside and inside the building to establish a quantitative baseline for RQ assessing the need for improvements.
UR12	s.7	Functional	The system should collect and analyze data on mobility patterns to improve Indoor Environment Quality (IEQ) and facilitate the optimal use of the indoor space.
UR13	s.7	Functional	INHERIT should relate mobility data with thermal comfort to identify correlations and optimize comfort and efficiency
UR14	s.9	Functional	The system should provide access to a hub of data related to CH buildings and historical renovation plans.
UR15	s.9	Functional	Promote engagement with facility managers of CH buildings to gather insights into renovation experiences, challenges faced, and solutions implemented.
UR16	s.1, s.6	Functional	Creation of detailed BIM and BEM models to support renovation planning and energy performance assessment under different renovation scenarios.
UR17	s.1	Functional	Implementation of AR/VR interfaces to visualize renovation designs and scenarios.
UR18	s.1	Non-functional	The system should ensure user-friendly interfaces to facilitate the implementation and long-term durability of preventive maintenance practices.
UR19	s.1, s.8	Functional	Use of building data to develop a comprehensive H-BIM model to support preventive maintenance.
UR20	s.3	Functional	The system should allow and promote collaboration with various stakeholders to facilitate decisions towards optimal financing.

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

UR (ID)	Related Service (ID)	Functional/ Non-Functional	Brief Description
UR21	s.0	Functional	INHERIT should deploy sensors and monitoring equipment and develop a platform for sharing data among relevant stakeholders.
UR22	s.6, s.8	Functional	Enrichment of the BIM model with data obtained from inspections and plan interventions based on various scenarios
UR23	s.9	Functional	The system will utilize GIS modeling data for effective mapping and replication.

Table 9: Consolidated User Requirements

The following Figure 2 provides a clear and structured mapping that connects each finalised UR to the specific INHERIT services. This cross-reference ensures full traceability, showing exactly which technical solution addresses each identified user's need. By viewing the requirements alongside their corresponding services, it becomes easy to see how the project's functional and non-functional goals are distributed across the different services in the toolkit.

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	s.0	s.1	s.2	s.3	s.4	s.5	s.6	s.7	s.8	s.9	s.10
UR01	X				X	X					
UR02			X	X						X	
UR03					X					X	
UR04				X		X					
UR05				X		X					
UR06					X						
UR07						X		X			
UR08			X				X		X		
UR09	X										X
UR10	X										X
UR11					X						
UR12								X			
UR13								X			
UR14										X	
UR15										X	
UR16		X					X				
UR17		X									
UR18		X									
UR19		X							X		
UR20				X							
UR21	X										
UR22							X		X		
UR23										X	

Figure 2: Mapping User Requirements to INHERIT Services

3.3 Workshop – 1° Round of the Co-creation Activities

3.3.1 Workshop Implementation and Participation

The first round of the co-creation workshop took place online on 19 May 2024, bringing together representatives from all eight INHERIT pilots, service providers, and end users from sectors relevant to CH. The workshop gathered 44 participants from various European countries, achieving a balanced gender distribution (56% female, 44% male). Attendees included researchers, application developers, engineers, architects, and other relevant professionals.

Figure 3: Screenshot from the 1st co-creation workshop of the INHERIT services

3.3.2 Structure of the 1st Co-creation Workshop

The first co-creation workshop aimed to engage end users and stakeholders in refining and expanding the user requirements for the INHERIT services. This workshop provided a collaborative setting where participants could review the initial requirements identified internally by the project team and contribute their perspectives to ensure the services were aligned with real user needs.

In the first activity, Refining the User Requirements, participants were divided into three break-out rooms, each corresponding to a specific group of services. Within each room, participants spent 10–15 minutes reviewing each service and discussing the user requirements that had been identified internally. They were encouraged to provide additional requirements from the end-user perspective, highlighting features or functionalities that might have been overlooked. Once the brainstorming was complete, participants prioritized the requirements using the MoSCoW method, which classifies requirements as **Must-haves, Should-haves, Could-haves, and Won't-haves**. This process ensured that the development team could distinguish essential features from optional ones and incorporate end-user insights into the service design.

In the second activity, Data Collection Enablers, the participants focused on identifying the types of data that could support the services. They reviewed each service carefully, considering the data needed to enable functionality and improve service delivery. This step helped ensure that the services would be grounded in relevant, actionable data.

In the final activity, Drivers and Barriers for Services, the stakeholders examined potential facilitators and obstacles to the development of the services. Participants reviewed datasets previously identified by the project team, evaluating their relevance and suitability for each service. They selected datasets that best aligned with service needs, helping to highlight both opportunities and challenges in service implementation.

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Overall, the first co-creation workshop allowed end users to actively contribute to the development of the INHERIT services, validating internally identified requirements and adding new insights. The workshop fostered a user-centered approach, ensuring that the services reflected real user needs and expectations while also identifying data opportunities and potential barriers for effective implementation.

Figure 4: Screenshot from the break-out rooms during the 1st co-creation workshop of the INHERIT services

3.3.3 Feedback received from the 1st Co-creation Workshop

Table 7 presents the consolidated User Requirements (URs) identified during the first co-creation workshop, incorporating inputs from both service providers and stakeholders. It illustrates the relationship between each UR and the corresponding INHERIT service, as well as their prioritization according to the MoSCoW classification (Must have, Should have, Could have, and Won't have). Following this initial mapping, a further refinement and consolidation process was carried out, resulting in the final set of URs presented in **Section 3.3**.

No	S	UR	Must	Should	Could	Won't
UR1.1	s.1	Visualize renovation designs (e.g. aesthetics, energy outcomes, costs, accessibility) and scenarios through AR/VR interfaces (upon availability of data from the simulation backend tools)				
UR1.2	s.1	The system should ensure user-friendly interfaces to facilitate the implementation and long-term durability of preventive maintenance practices.				

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

No	S	UR	Must	Should	Could	Won't
UR1.3	s.1	Visualization of different maintenance scenarios				
UR1.4	s.1	Visualize maintenance process through AR/VR for training purposes				
UR1.5	s.1	Visualize the CH site before and after major renovation milestones (upon availability of the historical designs)				
UR1.6	s.1	Visualize hazard identification and mitigation measures through AR/VR for training purposes (upon availability of data from simulation tools)				
UR1.7	s.1	Use AR/VR to interact with digital artifacts, see inside reconstructed buildings, or experience historical events as if they were there.				
UR2.1	s.2	The system provides strategies to recommend energy efficiency measures (and provide the estimated energy savings in different granularities monthly, yearly etc.)				
UR2.2	s.2	The system provides strategies to recommend strategies for minimizing costs.				
UR2.3	s.2	The system should provide recommendations for comfort level upon availability of data related to heat / electricity consumption and air quality				
UR2.4	s.2	The system will evaluate the energy performance of the building in terms of long-term energy savings and comfort, under different building simulations (upon availability of data)				
UR2.5	s.2	Consider different building scenarios wrt. different heating schedules based on specific thermostat setpoints and the respective energy consumption				
UR2.6	s2	Examine renewable measures as part of potential interventions				
UR3.1	s.3	The system should support the selection of optimal renovation actions, including Costs and energy savings, for CH building (upon availability of buildings' energy performance data and estimation of energy requirements for each renovation proposal)				
UR3.2	s.3	The system should compile a list of renovation plans and assess the financial and energy savings of each plan to propose the most suitable (depending on the data provided)				
UR3.3	s.3	The system should allow and promote collaboration with various stakeholders to facilitate decisions towards optimal financing.				
UR3.4	s.3	Estimation of economic parameters like life-cycle costs				

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

No	S	UR	Must	Should	Could	Won't
UR3.5	s.3	The tool would need to be simple and easy to add renovations of different types				
UR3.6	s.3	The tool can integrate the criteria. The users can indicate which of the criteria used are more important to them, different stakeholders have different priorities and assess different criteria with different weights.				
UR3.7	s.3	The tool could be provided as a user-friendly app				
UR4.1	s.4	The system should get available data from air quality smart meters installed within the indoor environment. The system should collect and process data related to indoor comfort (e.g. humidity and air quality).				
UR4.2	s.4	The system should ensure frequent updates and timely delivery of collected data to support rapid analysis and decision-making.				
UR4.3	s.4	The system should perform reliable analysis of collected data to identify patterns and trends. / Analyze collected data to generate insights, e.g., display figures of non-comfort hours per year and per space, be able to see statistics and identify trends and patterns for indoor quality				
UR4.4	s.4	The system should perform reliable analysis of collected data to identify anomalies related to indoor comfort.				
UR4.5	s.4	Provide tailored recommendations for optimizing operational and behavioral practices (Make sure the hard measures proposed are feasible (link with s.3))/ Recommendations should be promptly delivered to users, enabling interventions to optimize indoor comfort. / The system should collect air quality data, analyze them and provide recommendations on the improvement of building's energy performance. / Provide customized suggestions tailored to the use of the buildings				
UR4.6	s.4	Evaluate noise levels both outside and inside the building to establish a quantitative baseline for assessing the need for improvements.				
UR4.7	s.4	Enable live feedback from users; Chat/Alert with facility manager based on the feedback received				
UR5.1	s.5	The system should have available data related to energy consumption, including historical energy usage data, current consumption levels, renewable energy sources (RES), and other energy assets. The system should gather data related to energy consumption.				

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

No	S	UR	Must	Should	Could	Won't
UR5.2	s.5	The system should analyze the data and provide detailed insights into energy consumption trends (e.g. peak demand periods and inefficiencies) to facilitate informed decision-making / Use of quantitative measures to provide insights; Figures with consumption per hour and weekday	Must			
UR5.3	s.5	Based on the analysis of energy consumption and performance data, the system should generate recommendations for improving energy efficiency and performance. / Provide tailored recommendations to improve energy consumption / energy performance, e.g., Proposed load shifting based on peaks		Should		
UR5.4	s.5	The system will facilitate credible consumption forecasting.	Must			
UR5.5	s.5	Modify recommendations based on the objectives set (e.g., Estimation of costs on cheapest hours (based on pricing from electricity provider)			Could	
UR5.6	s.5	Provide recommendation based on the ranking with energy-intensive equipment				Won't
UR6.1	s.6	The system will visualize the BIM model of the pilot buildings (based on user input/upload of BIM model)	Must			
UR6.2	s.6	The system will use data from inspections, integrate it into the BIM model			Could	
UR6.3	s.6	The system will be able to plan interventions based on various scenarios (for example get estimates of energy savings given a certain action (e.g. improved efficiency of HVAC system)				Won't
UR6.4	s.6	The system will evaluate the building's energy efficiency and identify areas for improvement to reduce energy costs.	Must			
UR6.5	s.6	The system will support preventive maintenance			Could	
UR6.6	s.6	The system will visualize energy intensity of energy uses (live vs. historical)	Must			
UR6.7	s.6	The system will use data from sensors e.g., to get insights for each room about different conditions (energy consumption, thermal quality)		Should		
UR6.8	s.6	The system will simulate impact of behavioral changes			Could	
UR7.1	s.7	The system should gather data related to crowd movement, analyse them and provide insights.	Must			
UR7.2	s.7	The system should provide effective strategies to optimize space utilization.	Must			

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

No	S	UR	Must	Should	Could	Won't
UR7.3	s.7	The system integrates the mobility data with thermal comfort to identify correlations and optimize comfort and efficiency				
UR7.4	s.7	The system should collect and analyze data on mobility patterns to improve Indoor Environment Quality (IEQ) and facilitate the optimal use of the indoor space.				
UR7.5	s.7	Trigger alarms for facility managers when spaces are over occupied				
UR8.1	s.8	H-BIM will collect data from technical inspections, integrate them into the model and assist in decision-making				
UR8.2	s.8	H-BIM allows analysing different scenarios to identify improvement actions to reduce energy costs				
UR8.3	s.8	H-BIM needs to be accurate and result in a complete 3D model that captures all relevant building information as a basis for preventive maintenance of heritage buildings.				
UR8.4	s.8	H-BIM will provide user-friendly visualisation to facilitate the implementation and long-term durability of preventive maintenance practices.				
UR8.5	s.8	H-BIM should integrate useful and realistic data on material characterisation and building system characteristics.				
UR8.6	s.8	Use of RES technologies in Cultural Heritage				
UR8.7	s.8	H-BIM should be an interoperable, multi-level model that encourages communication and collaboration between users.				
UR8.8	s.8	H-BIM must be alive, able to grow and evolve according to future changes in line with the life cycle of the building.				
UR9.1	s.9	The system should provide access to a hub of data related to CH buildings; Kind of information: year of construction, information about refurbishment, architectural style, image, historical value and protection level				
UR9.2	s.9	The system should provide access to historical renovation plans; Approximate cost of maintenance				
UR9.3	s.9	The system gathers insights into renovation experiences, challenges faced, and solutions implemented.				
UR9.4	s.9	The system will utilize GIS modeling data for effective mapping and replication.				

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

No	S	UR	Must	Should	Could	Won't
UR9.5	s.9	The system should enable clustering functionality (There should be the same type of buildings to ensure that user trust the service calculation. For example, I, as church building owner, am interested to be compared / or explore other buildings that are also churches.); Criteria for similar buildings: morphological building regulations, fixed patterns, distinctive elements (e.g. blue windows/doors)				
UR9.6	s.9	Incorporate data related to the region of the buildings, such as economic data, so that the stakeholders can know about the development dynamic of an area; Provide information on the respective legislation regarding building rules/restrictions and local planning				
UR9.7	s.9	Possibility to select the main parameter to categorise/cluster the building				
UR10.1	s.10	The system should be able to simulate and analyze various climate scenarios related to extreme temperatures to assess their potential impacts on the pilot building.				
UR10.2	s.10	The system should be able to simulate and analyze various climate scenarios related to heavy rainfall to assess their potential impact on the pilot building, such as an increase in the intensity of rainwater				
UR10.3	s.10	The system should be able to simulate and analyze various climate scenarios related to wind risk to assess their potential impacts on the pilot building.				
UR10.4	s.10	The system should be able to simulate and analyze various climate scenarios related to fire, level of dust, and drought to assess their potential impact on the pilot building.				
UR10.5	s.10	The analysis should lead to the calculation of relevant KPIs associated with each climate scenario.				
UR10.6	s.10	The system should simulate climate-related hazards and assess their impact both at city and at building levels.				
UR10.7	s.10	Modelling of outdoor environmental conditions under various long-term climate scenarios. [Indoor environmental conditions (or demand forecast) for different extreme weather scenarios. It can display information on past events, together with the present and some forecast of future environmental conditions.]				
UR10.8	s.10	The system should visualize the results in a map-based application: floods - map				

Table 10: URs categorisation per service and MoSCoW prioritization

For the final activity, participants conducted a structured SWOT analysis to assess the internal and external factors influencing the development and application of the INHERIT tools and methodologies. The results are summarized below.

Internal Factors: Strengths and Weaknesses

The INHERIT toolkit is recognized for its strong methodological foundation, particularly its ability to provide structured, evidence-based support for decision-making in the CH sector. Stakeholders highlighted the framework's adaptability across various sites and its role in increasing transparency and risk-preparedness awareness. However, these strengths are balanced by certain internal limitations. Specifically, the precision of the tools is often dependent on data availability, which can be limited or fragmented at some sites. Furthermore, the technical complexity of the tools may require a level of local expertise or capacity that is not always readily available, highlighting a need for better data harmonization and user support.

External Factors: Opportunities and Threats

Regarding the external environment, there is a clear **policy alignment** with current global priorities. The increasing focus on climate change and resilience creates a significant opportunity for the cross-sectoral uptake of the INHERIT methodology. There is a **growing demand** for the exact type of participatory, evidence-based risk assessment that this project provides. Nevertheless, external threats must be managed to ensure long-term success. These include the inherent difficulty of accurately quantifying complex environmental hazards and the potential **for financial constraints** at the local level. To prevent limited uptake, the project must focus on ensuring the tools are perceived as **cost-effective and user-friendly**, rather than resource intensive.

4 Phase B: Co-creating Use-friendly Environments

4.1 User-flow Diagrams

The second phase of the project played a crucial role in shaping the co-creation of the front-end for the INHERIT services. This phase occurred after the submission of the first wave of INHERIT services and before the launch of the second wave. Its timing was particularly important, as it allowed service providers to gather and reflect on feedback regarding the initial version of their services. During this period, providers had the opportunity to assess the strengths and weaknesses of their prototypes and make informed adjustments based on the insights and recommendations shared during the second co-creation workshop, which was held in December 2024. By integrating this iterative feedback process, the second phase ensured that the development of the front-end was closely aligned with user needs and expectations, and it provided a structured framework for continuous improvement before the release of the second wave of services.

4.2 Workshop – 2nd Round of the Co-creation Activities

4.2.1 Workshop Implementation and Participation

The second co-creation workshop was held online on 13 December 2024. Following dissemination of the event through the project's and partners' social media channels, a total of 43 participants registered, 20 of whom were external stakeholders from diverse professional backgrounds, including architects, project managers, engineers, and researchers. Among the attendees, 56% were female and 44% were male.

4.2.2 Structure of the 2nd Co-creation Workshop

The second co-creation workshop was structured around two interactive group activities designed to collect structured and qualitative feedback from participants regarding the services under development.

During the first activity, Service Presentation and Structured Feedback Session, participants were divided into three (3) parallel working groups to ensure active engagement and balanced discussion.

During this session, each service provider presented an overview of their respective service, including its overall concept, key functionalities, core features, and intended user benefits. The objective was to familiarise participants with the scope and operational logic of each service prior to feedback collection.

Following the presentations, participants were invited to provide feedback through a combination of:

- Multiple-choice questions, aimed at gathering structured and comparable input on usability, clarity, relevance, and perceived value; and
- Open-ended questions, allowing participants to elaborate on strengths, potential improvements, risks, and additional suggestions.

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

This activity enabled the collection of both quantitative and qualitative insights, supporting a comprehensive assessment of the services from diverse stakeholder perspectives.

Figure 5: Example of the first co-creation activity of the 2nd Workshop

The second activity, User Flow Validation and Co-Design Session, participants remained divided into three (3) groups. Participants were then invited to critically review the proposed user journeys and actively contribute by:

- Suggesting additional steps that may be required for completeness;
- Identifying optional steps that could enhance flexibility or user experience; and
- Providing comments on clarity, logic, usability, and potential bottlenecks.

This co-design approach allowed stakeholders to validate the proposed workflows and contribute to their refinement, ensuring that the services align with user expectations, practical needs, and real-world operational contexts.

Figure 6: Example of the second co-creation activity of the 2nd Workshop

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

4.2.3 Feedback received from the 2nd Co-creation Workshop

During the 2nd co-creation workshop on digital tools for heritage building design, renovation, and maintenance provided valuable insights into how technology can support preservation, energy efficiency, and user comfort. Participants evaluated a range of services, from AR/VR interfaces to energy forecasting and GIS-based platforms, and shared feedback on their usability, effectiveness, and practical value. Across all tools, there was strong agreement on the importance of accuracy, real-time data, and actionable insights for decision-making in heritage building management. Below is a list of the feedback received per service.

Service	Key Stakeholder Feedback	Priority Enhancements & Suggestions
s.1 Interactive screen use and AR-VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction	Valued real-time defect data and high-precision structural visualization.	Add cost estimation, photographic evidence of failures, and ranked intervention options.
s.2 Modelling and simulation environment	Must align with heritage principles; cost-benefit analysis is essential.	Include zone-specific modeling and guidance on financial incentives.
s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Intuitive visuals (sliders/color codes) significantly improve usability.	Group rooms by floor and highlight the proportion of preserved historic elements.
s.4 IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation	Preferred end-of-week forecasting windows for better planning.	Highlight the duration of optimization tasks to improve scheduling.
s.5 Energy forecasting and intelligent management	Pathology monitoring (humidity/CO ₂) and predictive maintenance are high value.	Improve alarm systems and long-term maintenance expense projections.
s.6 Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring and management	Privacy is a priority; sensors are preferred over cameras.	Develop heat maps and event frequency summaries for better visualization.
s.7 Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	Automated notifications for facades and roofs are the highest priority.	Integrate tracking for overdue tasks and monitor material degradation.
s.9 GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	Building cluster visualization supports strategic neighborhood planning.	Implement color-coded pins and neighborhood selection filters.
s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	Future climate projections are highly valued for building-level risk.	Add step-by-step tutorials and more indicators for potential physical impact.

Table 11: Key results from the 2nd co-creation workshop of the INHERIT services

5 Phase C: Services Demonstrations and Final Refinements

5.1 Development of Services Demos

The third phase of the co-creation process for the INHERIT solutions aims to provide stakeholders with a demo version of the services, enabling them to deliver final feedback prior to completion. This step allows service providers to incorporate any necessary refinements and optimisations before submitting the final revised versions in the third wave of the INHERIT solutions.

To support this objective, a third and final co-creation workshop was organised in November 2025. Stakeholders who had participated in previous sessions were invited to ensure continuity, while the group was broadened to include additional stakeholders. This wider participation was considered essential, as the feedback required at this stage focused specifically on the services themselves, particularly their usability, relevance, and practical applicability for professionals working in cultural heritage, engineering, and architecture.

5.2 Workshop – 3rd Round of the Co-creation Activities

5.2.1 Workshop Implementation and Participation

The third round of the co-creation workshop for the INHERIT services was held online on 18 November 2025. The workshop was promoted through email invitations and dissemination activities via the project's LinkedIn page and the LinkedIn pages of project partners. A registration form was included in the promotional material, resulting in 28 registrations. Of the 28 registered participants, 10 were external stakeholders and 18 were internal participants, including service providers and other project partners. In terms of gender distribution, 10 participants (36%) were male and 18 (64%) were female.

The external stakeholders represented a diverse range of professional backgrounds, including energy departments, CH managers, project managers, and directors.

Figure 7: Screenshot from the 3rd co-creation workshop of the INHERIT services

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Although several external stakeholders registered during the promotion of the workshop, only three ultimately attended the session. Despite this lower-than-expected external participation, all INHERIT partners, together with the attending external stakeholders and service providers, had the opportunity to review, assess, and discuss the refinement of the services.

Partners who were not directly involved in the technical development of the services provided valuable and constructive feedback, offering a more independent perspective to support further improvements.

5.2.2 Structure of the 3rd Co-creation Workshop

The third co-creation workshop was organised around three interactive activities designed to gather structured and targeted feedback on the demo versions of the INHERIT services. The overall objective was to assess participants' perceptions, evaluate the perceived value of the services, and collect concrete suggestions to support their final refinement.

The first activity, Journey of Perception, began with the division of participants into three groups to facilitate focused discussion. Within each group, the respective Service Providers presented a demonstration of their service. Following each presentation, participants were invited to reflect on their perceptions at three distinct moments: prior to the demonstration, capturing their initial expectations; immediately after the presentation, reflecting their first impression; and finally, their level of understanding of the service and its functionality. This exercise helped identify whether the services' objectives and value propositions were clearly communicated and how perceptions evolved after the demonstration.

The second activity, User Value Mapping, aimed to evaluate the relevance and usefulness of each service from the participants' perspective. Each service was represented visually and positioned within a two-dimensional matrix defined by usefulness (ranging from low to high) and relevance (also ranging from low to high). Participants placed each service within the matrix according to their assessment. This visual mapping provided an immediate overview of which services were perceived as delivering higher practical value and importance within the stakeholders' professional context.

The third activity, Service Feedback Mapping, focused on collecting more detailed and structured feedback. A matrix was presented including three analytical dimensions: strengths, risks or barriers, and ideas for improvement. Participants contributed feedback for each service by identifying positive aspects, potential challenges in implementation or adoption, and suggestions for further enhancement. This activity enabled the systematic capture of actionable insights, directly informing the final adjustments of the INHERIT services before their final release.

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Figure 8: Screenshot from the third activity of the 3rd co-creation workshop

5.2.3 Feedback received from the 3rd Co-creation Workshop

Table 12 summarises the outcomes of the three activities. Through all groups, participants generally found the services to be highly relevant, though specific technical and interface improvements were suggested to ensure ease of use for non-technical stakeholders.

	Activity 1	Activity 2	Activity 3-Detailed Feedback (Strengths, Risks, Ideas)
s.1	Satisfactory	Highly Relevant & Useful	S: Clear presentation of planned actions. R: High equipment costs and limited availability. I: Develop a dedicated interface to display results.
s.2	Satisfactory	Highly Relevant & Useful	S: Comprehensive scope. R: Potential complexity for the end-user. I: Simplify the user interface for better accessibility.
s.3	Low Understanding	Highly Relevant & Useful	S: High perceived utility. R: Unclear logic and risks regarding data availability. I: Create an interface that simplifies service interaction.
s.4	Satisfactory	Highly Relevant & Useful	S: Strong daily insights on lighting, comfort, and energy. R: Risk of data under-utilisation or sensor maintenance issues. I: Link dashboards with smart controls and cost-saving alerts.

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	Activity 1	Activity 2	Activity 3-Detailed Feedback (Strengths, Risks, Ideas)
s.5	Satisfactory	Highly Relevant & Useful	S: Enables clear planning and budgeting for energy upgrades. R: Reliability depends heavily on data quality/assumptions. I: Include a scenario tool with benchmarks for behavioral change.
s.6	Satisfactory	Highly Relevant & Useful	S: High volume of useful info accessible via building model. R: High risk of information overload for the user. I: Add simulations for energy savings based on renovation types.
s.7	Satisfactory	Highly Relevant & Useful	S: Critical data that supports IEQ and energy forecasting. R: Privacy/sharing constraints regarding specific room usage. I: Combine sensor data with staff observations and event calendars.
s.8	Not available feedback on this service		
s.9	Satisfactory	Highly Relevant & Useful	S: Highly attractive and visual mapping features. R: Data accuracy risks. I: Provide clear conclusions (e.g., "For this building type, X is recommended").
s.10	Satisfactory	Highly Relevant & Useful	S: Accessible language; suitable for non-technical users. R: Scaling the solution to larger heritage clusters. I: Improve navigation between different climate scenarios.

Table 12: Multi-Dimensional Validation of INHERIT Services: Perception, Value, and Technical Feedback

Conclusions

Deliverable D2.3 marks a key milestone in aligning stakeholder engagement with the technical development of the INHERIT Decision Support Services. Through a structured three-phase co-creation methodology, the project successfully translated stakeholder needs into validated user requirements and refined service functionalities.

The process demonstrated several important achievements:

- The **systematic identification and mapping of user stories** across eight pilot sites ensured that services respond to real-world operational challenges in diverse cultural heritage contexts.
- The **consolidation of functional and non-functional user requirements** established a clear traceability framework linking stakeholder input to specific INHERIT services.
- Iterative **co-creation workshops enabled validation, prioritisation, and refinement of services**, interfaces, and workflows.
- **Structured feedback mechanisms**, including MoSCoW prioritisation, SWOT analysis, user journey validation, and value mapping exercises, strengthened the robustness and usability of the services.

The results confirm that stakeholder-driven development significantly enhances service relevance, clarity, and practical applicability. Feedback consistently highlighted the importance of data reliability, usability for non-technical users, interoperability, and cost-effectiveness, aspects that have been integrated into the final service refinements.

At the same time, the process identified key challenges, particularly related to data availability, technical complexity, and scalability across heterogeneous heritage contexts. Addressing these challenges remains essential to ensuring long-term adoption and replication beyond the project duration.

Overall, the co-creation framework implemented under WP2 establishes a replicable model for integrating social innovation into technical solution development. By embedding stakeholder participation throughout the design and validation cycle, INHERIT strengthens the sustainability, inclusiveness, and resilience of its Decision Support Services.

This deliverable therefore provides not only a consolidation of requirements but also a validated methodological foundation supporting the successful deployment and future scalability of the INHERIT solutions across the European cultural heritage sector.

References

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Leffingwell, D. (2011). *Agile Software Requirements: Lean Requirements Practices for Teams, Programs, and the Enterprise*. Addison-Wesley.

Schwaber, K., & Beedle, M. (2002). *Agile Software Development with Scrum*. Prentice Hall.

Annex A

Pilot 1 - City Administration Headquarters, Croatia

User Scenario ID	US [1.1]																							
User Scenario Title	Sensors and monitoring system																							
Pilot	Pilot 1																							
Relevant Service(s)	s.0 Heritage buildings smartification & data exchange																							
Description	The INHERIT Smartification and Data Exchange Platform will be delivered. The components will include sensors and monitoring systems to collect and share data about the heritage building's condition and performance to analyse and interpret the collected data (link with s.4 and s.5).																							
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Installation of sensors and monitoring system 2. Collecting and analysing the data collected 																							
Potential Barriers	N/A																							
Equipment	<p>No relevant equipment is installed. The plan for the equipment to be procured and installed for the needs of the INHERIT pilot is:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Equipment</th> <th colspan="3">Short description</th> </tr> <tr> <th>Equipment Name 1</th> <td colspan="3">Sensors and smart meters</td> </tr> </thead> </table>				Equipment	Short description			Equipment Name 1	Sensors and smart meters														
Equipment	Short description																							
Equipment Name 1	Sensors and smart meters																							
Datasets	<p>There is no relevant existing dataset. The plan for the datasets to be collected for the needs of the INHERIT pilot is:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Data Sets</th> <th>Short description</th> <th>Size</th> <th>Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)</th> <th>Means for data collection</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Energy consumption - electricity</td> <td>kWh</td> <td></td> <td>Open to certain level</td> <td>ISGE system (national database)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Heat consumption</td> <td>kWh</td> <td></td> <td>Open to certain level</td> <td>ISGE system (national database)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Natural gas consumption</td> <td>m³ / kWh</td> <td></td> <td>Open to certain level</td> <td>ISGE system (national database)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection	Energy consumption - electricity	kWh		Open to certain level	ISGE system (national database)	Heat consumption	kWh		Open to certain level	ISGE system (national database)	Natural gas consumption	m ³ / kWh		Open to certain level	ISGE system (national database)
Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection																				
Energy consumption - electricity	kWh		Open to certain level	ISGE system (national database)																				
Heat consumption	kWh		Open to certain level	ISGE system (national database)																				
Natural gas consumption	m ³ / kWh		Open to certain level	ISGE system (national database)																				

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	Water consumption	m ³		Open to certain level	ISGE system (national database)
	Indoor temperature	Degree C		Open to users	Installed sensors
	CO ₂ concentration	ppm		Open to users	Installed sensors
	CO concentration	ppm		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Atmosphere pressure	Pa/kPa/bar		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Relative humidity	%		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Indoor PM ₁ concentration	µm/m ³		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Indoor PM _{2.5} concentration	µm/m ³		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Indoor PM ₁₀ concentration	µm/m ³		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC)	µm/m ³		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Light level sensor	lux		Open to users	Installed sensors

User Scenario ID	US [1.2]
User Scenario Title	Optimal renovation strategies
Pilot	Pilot 1
Relevant Service(s)	s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning
Description	The end user will get insight in suggested renovation actions and support in the decision-making process towards optimal financing. The renovation actions will be suggested considering special conditions regarding interventions in protected zone in which the pilot building is located and considering the climate risks.
Needs	1. The existing EPC for the pilot building is from 2011, so it is necessary to propose new renovation actions (considering the new energy performance data from s.5) with estimated potential savings (financial and energy)

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> There is a need for a new audit of the building to have better insight into the current condition of building components and technical systems Select the optimal renovation actions for the CH building considering the climate risks 				
Potential Barriers	Barriers due to the restrictions and special conditions regarding interventions in protected zone in which the pilot building is located.				
Equipment	No relevant equipment is installed.				
	Equipment		Short description		
	Equipment Name 1				
Datasets	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Name 1	Dataset from existing EPC		Open to certain level	Existing EPC, IEC database
	Dataset Name 2	Data on energy and water consumption monitored through the national information system for energy management called ISGE		Open to certain level	ISGE system (national database)
	Dataset Name 3	Dataset from new audit of building		Open to certain level	Audit

User Scenario ID	US [1.3]
User Scenario Title	Measured and quantified thermal comfort and air quality
Pilot	Pilot 1
Relevant Service(s)	s.4 Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimization
Description	The end user will be able to access data regarding thermal comfort and air quality and work on comfort optimisation. Through this service it will be assured that indoor conditions will guarantee end user's feeling of well-being. The existing data collected through the s.0 will be the starting point.
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Collect and monitor the data from air quality smart meters

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	2. Analyse the data and provide the recommendations on actions for comfort optimisation				
Potential Barriers	Behavioural impact on comfort optimisation could be potential barrier.				
Equipment	No relevant equipment is installed.				
	Equipment	Short description			
	Equipment Name 1				
Datasets	There is no relevant existing dataset.				
	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Indoor temperature	Degree C		Open to users	Installed sensors
	CO2 concentration	ppm		Open to users	Installed sensors
	CO concentration	ppm		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Atmosphere pressure	Pa/kPa/bar		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Relative humidity	%		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Indoor PM1 concentration	µm/m3		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Indoor PM2.5 concentration	µm/m3		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Indoor PM10 concentration	µm/m3		Open to users	Installed sensors
	Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC)	µm/m3		Open to users	Installed sensors
Light level sensor	lux		Open to users	Installed sensors	

User Scenario ID	US [1.4]
User Scenario Title	Energy performance analysis
Pilot	Pilot 1

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Relevant Service(s)	s.5 Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management					
Description	The end user will be able to access data regarding energy consumption, energy forecasting, as well as recommendations for improved energy performance. The focus will be on energy forecasting (for building, RES and other energy assets), forecasting models for indoor temperature and humidity (linked to s.4) and optimisation with the goal of increasing flexibility potential of pilot building.					
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse energy consumption and energy performance Provide recommendation on actions to improve and optimise energy performance 					
Potential Barriers	Barriers due to the restrictions and special conditions regarding interventions in protected zone in which the pilot building is located.					
Equipment	No relevant equipment is installed.					
	Equipment	Short description				
	Equipment Name 1					
Datasets	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Level (Open or Private)	Diss. (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Name 1	Energy performance certificate				
	Dataset Name 2	Energy bills				

User Scenario ID	US [1.5]	
User Scenario Title	KPIs impacted by different climate scenarios	
Pilot	Pilot 1	
Relevant Service(s)	s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	
Description	This service will enable to assess the most relevant impacts affecting pilot building according to the most prominent climate hazards. The service will allow to calculate relevant KPIs from the assessment and monitoring framework that will be impacted by different climate scenarios.	
Needs	Analyse the impact by different climate scenarios	
Potential Barriers	N/A	
Equipment	No relevant equipment is installed.	
	Equipment	Short description

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Equipment Name 1																					
Datasets	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Data Sets</th> <th>Short description</th> <th>Size</th> <th>Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)</th> <th>Means for data collection</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Dataset Name 1</td> <td>Available climate data</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dataset Name 2</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dataset Name 3</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection	Dataset Name 1	Available climate data				Dataset Name 2					Dataset Name 3				
	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection																
	Dataset Name 1	Available climate data																			
	Dataset Name 2																				
Dataset Name 3																					

Pilot 3 - ELLET Building under Acropolis, Greece

User Scenario ID	US [3.1]				
User Scenario Title	Operational recommendations for noise comfort and air quality				
Pilot	Pilot 3				
Relevant Service(s)	s.4 Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimization				
Description	The user will be able to access field data regarding noise pollution, air quality and humidity. This will provide a quantitative baseline to understand better the comfort levels. In addition, the user will receive recommendations on behavioral actions (e.g., opening windows, ...) based on real-time insights.				
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Noise pollution at the facade should be measured; Maybe it could be measured outside and inside the building to have a quantitative baseline to identify the need (the replacement of traditional windows is costly). Monitor the air quality inside the building. The city center has poor air quality, and we need to get information about how this is affecting the air indoors. Collect data about the humidity especially in the underground floor, where the ground is exposed due to the antiquities. Based on the data, provide recommendations for operational/behavioral optimization. 				
Potential Barriers	It is not possible to predict if by following the final operational recommendations that the overall performance of the building will be improved.				
Equipment	<p>No relevant equipment is installed. The plan for the equipment to be procured and installed for the needs of the INHERIT pilot is:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Equipment</th> <th>Short description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Equipment Name 1</td> <td>TBD (sensors to measure noise, air quality and humidity)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Equipment	Short description	Equipment Name 1	TBD (sensors to measure noise, air quality and humidity)
Equipment	Short description				
Equipment Name 1	TBD (sensors to measure noise, air quality and humidity)				
Datasets	There is no relevant existing dataset.				

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Name 1	-	-	-	-

User Scenario ID	US [3.2]														
User Scenario Title	Energy performance analysis														
Pilot	Pilot 3														
Relevant Service(s)	s.5 Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management														
Description	The user will be able to access field data regarding energy consumption, energy prediction (short-term, mid-term), as well as recommendations at operational level for improved energy performance.														
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collect data to get insights (based on quantitative measures), for instance, to understand better the heat loss. 2. Analyze patterns on energy consumption /energy performance. 3. Provide recommendation on actions to improve energy performance (e.g., pre-heating/ thermal load shifting). 														
Potential Barriers	N/A														
Equipment	No relevant equipment is installed. The plan for the equipment to be procured and installed for the needs of the INHERIT pilot is: <table border="1" data-bbox="438 1317 1445 1541"> <thead> <tr> <th>Equipment</th> <th>Short description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Equipment Name 1</td> <td>TBD (sensors to measure heat loss especially on roof -material conductivity, resistance, thickness etc-)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>					Equipment	Short description	Equipment Name 1	TBD (sensors to measure heat loss especially on roof -material conductivity, resistance, thickness etc-)						
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Datasets	<table border="1" data-bbox="438 1570 1445 1796"> <thead> <tr> <th>Data Sets</th> <th>Short description</th> <th>Size</th> <th>Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)</th> <th>Means for data collection</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Dataset Name 1</td> <td>Energy bills</td> <td>Consumption per month</td> <td>Open</td> <td>?</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection	Dataset Name 1	Energy bills	Consumption per month	Open	?				
Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection											
Dataset Name 1	Energy bills	Consumption per month	Open	?											

User Scenario ID	US [3.3]
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D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

User Scenario Title	Operational recommendations for crowd and mobility management			
Pilot	Pilot 3			
Relevant Service(s)	s.7 Real-time Insights on activity and mobility patterns			
Description	The user will be able to access field data regarding mobility and crowd gathering inside the building in special occasions like site visits to the building's antiquities, conferences and workshops. Real-time insights regarding crowd management and thermal comfort will be provided.			
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gain insights into the crowd management to host more effectively site visits, workshops etc. 2. Gather mobility patterns and possibly combine with thermal comfort. (data from s.5 will be used) 			
Potential Barriers	N/A			
Equipment	No relevant equipment is installed. The plan for the equipment to be procured and installed for the needs of the INHERIT pilot is:			
	Equipment	Short description		
	Equipment Name 1	TBD (mobility sensors and crowd gathering calculators)		
Datasets	There is no relevant existing dataset.			
	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)
	Dataset Name 1			

Pilot 4 – Concert Hall, Latvia

User Scenario ID	US [4.1]
User Scenario Title	Visualization of energy performance of the building
Pilot	Pilot 4
Relevant Service(s)	s.2. Modelling and simulation environment
Description	The user will be able to see the building energy consumption and model the future consumption taking into consideration different conventional measures, improvement actions. The visualisation will let to predict the energy consumption in long term perspective thus giving a data-based arguments to discuss the need of building renovation with the City of Riga (the owner of the building).
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collect the data of consumed energy – heat; electricity. 2. Collect the data of indoor air quality – humidity; temperature; CO2. 3. Monitor the heat consumption in the building interacting with comfort level.

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	4. Based on the data provide recommendations for the energy optimization actions.				
Potential Barriers	The accuracy of evaluated performance and suggested measures.				
Equipment	No relevant equipment is installed. The plan for the equipment to be procured and installed for the needs of the INHERIT pilot is: Below are listed existing equipment in the building:				
	Equipment	Short description			
	Electricity meter	Each building in Latvia has individual electricity meter, the consumed electricity of the building.			
	Heat meter	Each building in Latvia has individual heat meter, which the delivered heat for the building.			
	Indoor air quality meters	The 12 indoor air quality sensors installed for the p needs.			
Datasets	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Electricity	kwh	tbc	Private	Data collected from the bills, excel format
	Dataset Heat	kWh	tbc	Private	Data gathered from platform, extracted in excel format
	Dataset CO2	ppm	tbc	Private	
	Dataset temperature	°C	tbc	Private	
	Dataset humidity	%	tbc	Private	
User Scenario ID	US [4.2]				
User Scenario Title	Renovation action plan				
Pilot	Pilot 4				
Relevant Service(s)	s.3. Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning				
Description	The user will be able see the suggested renovation actions for the building. The renovation actions will be suggested taking into consideration the needed financial resources and potential savings per action.				
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> List the potential actions that can be done under building renovation. Estimate the potential savings (both: financial and energy) of the renovation actions. Select the best renovation actions for the cultural heritage building. 				
Potential Barriers	Restrictions from the cultural heritage building controlling departments for suggested renovation actions.				
Equipment	No relevant equipment is installed.				
Datasets	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Electricity	kwh	tbc	Private	Data collected from the bills, excel format
	Dataset Heat	kWh	tbc	Private	
	Dataset CO2	ppm	tbc	Private	

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	Dataset temperature	°C	tbc	Private	Data gathered from platform, extracted in excel format
	Dataset humidity	%	tbc	Private	

User Scenario ID	US [4.3]												
User Scenario Title	Regulated indoor air quality												
Pilot	Pilot 4												
Relevant Service(s)	s.4 IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation												
Description	The user will better understand the air quality situation in building in general and in the selected rooms. It will let to evaluate the need to install thermoregulators and work on comfort optimisation actions.												
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collect and monitor the data from air quality smart meters. 2. Collect the data of humidity in different floors of the building (Important at spring in autumn period in the building basement). 3. Analyse the data and provide the recommendation on action to improve energy performance (e.g. install thermoregulators). 4. Provide suggestions on the energy needs according to the different use of the building (e.g. during the day it is used for the choir repetition, during events there are organized concerts with 300 seats in maximum). 												
Potential Barriers	The pilot building is used for two purposes. First, it is daily used as a place for the choir repetition, second it is also used as the place for concerts. The amount of people in the building during repetition and concerts significant differs, which means the actions for the optimisation must be created specifically based on building use. The solutions must be easy to implement.												
Equipment	<p>No relevant equipment is installed. The plan for the equipment to be procured and installed for the needs of the INHERIT pilot is:</p> <p>Below are listed existing equipment in the building:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Equipment</th> <th>Short description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Electricity meter</td> <td>Each building in Latvia has individual electricity meter, which sum the consumed electricity of the building.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Heat meter</td> <td>Each building in Latvia has individual heat meter, which sum the delivered heat for the building.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Indoor air quality meters</td> <td>The 12 indoor air quality sensors installed for the project needs.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>					Equipment	Short description	Electricity meter	Each building in Latvia has individual electricity meter, which sum the consumed electricity of the building.	Heat meter	Each building in Latvia has individual heat meter, which sum the delivered heat for the building.	Indoor air quality meters	The 12 indoor air quality sensors installed for the project needs.
Equipment	Short description												
Electricity meter	Each building in Latvia has individual electricity meter, which sum the consumed electricity of the building.												
Heat meter	Each building in Latvia has individual heat meter, which sum the delivered heat for the building.												
Indoor air quality meters	The 12 indoor air quality sensors installed for the project needs.												
Datasets	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection								
	Dataset Electricity	kwh	tbc	Private	Data collected from the bills, excel format								
	Dataset Heat	kWh	tbc	Private									
	Dataset CO2	ppm	tbc	Private	Data gathered from platform, extracted in excel format								
	Dataset temperature	°C	tbc	Private									
	Dataset humidity	%	tbc	Private									

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

User Scenario ID	US [4.4]
User Scenario Title	Clustered with other CH buildings
Pilot	Pilot 4
Relevant Service(s)	s.9 GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance
Description	The user will have possibility to find similar CH buildings and find the optimal maintenance plan, based on the buildings' classification and the INHERIT Hub.
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Get information about similar CH building renovation plans and results 2. Consult with the similar CH facility managers for the realization of the renovation (the challenges faced with the selected solutions)
Potential Barriers	Taking into consideration the CH building specific (Church, that is transferred to the concert hall) and the specific of climate conditions of Latvia (energy demand and possibility to install innovative energy production technologies) it may be hard to find similar CH buildings to cluster with.
Equipment	No relevant equipment is installed.
Datasets	No relevant dataset that could be leveraged by the service.

Pilot 5 - Social Residential Building, Poland

User Scenario ID	US [5.1]				
User Scenario Title	Sensor and monitoring system for building maintenance				
Pilot	Pilot 5				
Relevant Service(s)	s.0 Heritage buildings smartification data exchange s.6 Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real time monitoring and management s.8 Preventive maintenance with H BIM				
Description	Smartification of the building through the introduction of sensors and controllers linked to a data exchange platform accessible to stakeholders. The information collected and combined with the BIM model and monitoring of building's performance will enable the management, planning and preventive maintenance of the building. It would be recommended to have a as result of the service maintenance plan or recommendations.				
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Installation of sensors and monitoring systems 2. Data exchange on a platform available to stakeholders 3. Development of the BIM model 4. Analysis of data obtained from inspections, entered the BIM model and planning of interventions based on multiple scenarios 				
Potential Barriers	Lack of accessibility to all apartments.				
Equipment	No relevant equipment is installed. The plan for the equipment to be procured and installed for the needs of the INHERIT pilot is:				
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Equipment</th> <th>Short description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Equipment	Short description		
Equipment	Short description				

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	TBD	Sensors for Indoor Air Quality and smart meters in two flats
Datasets	There is no relevant existing dataset that could be leveraged by the service.	

User Scenario ID	US [5.2]					
User Scenario Title	Selection of the optimal renovation scenario based on energy performance data and AR/VR interface					
Pilot	Pilot 5					
Relevant Service(s)	s.1 Interactive screen use and AR VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning					
Description	The services will help to identify the most optimal renovation strategies. Before implementing physical changes to the building, AR and VR allow designers to create virtual prototypes and test renovation ideas. This helps in identifying potential challenges and refining design solutions without altering the actual structure. The idea is that building owners and occupants can see the building after renovation (building envelope) thanks to AR/VR (although the building is not renovated). Various renovation scenarios can be analyzed with VR/AR solutions. It would be good also to see some potential energy performance of the building for various scenarios.					
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Development of the BIM model 5. Development of the BEM model 6. AR/VR interface 					
Potential Barriers	Lack of accessibility to all apartments.					
Equipment	No relevant equipment is installed. The plan for the equipment to be procured and installed for the needs of the INHERIT pilot is:					
	Equipment	Short description				
	TBD	VR google				
Datasets	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Level (Open or Private)	Diss. (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Name 1	Energy bills				
	Dataset Name 2	BIM model				

Pilot 6 - Monastery “Ntra. Sra. Del Prado”, Spain

User Scenario ID	US [6.1]						
User Scenario Title	Checking the feasibility of preventive conservation and proper maintenance of CH buildings with HBIM and its cost-effective energy performance optimisation.						
Pilot	Pilot 6						
Relevant Service(s)	s.0 Heritage building smartification & data exchange s.1 Interactive screen use and AR-VR interface for heritage building design and renovation construction. s.6 Digital Twin for heritage facilities’ real-time monitoring and management s.8 Preventive maintenance with H BIM						
Description	The interconnection between services facilitates the testing of the feasibility of the methodology to be developed for the preventive maintenance and proper conservation of CH buildings making an efficient and sustainable use of the available resources and optimising the cost-effective energy of the buildings. It will be supported by using interactive screen AR-VR interface and Digital Twin, as well as through technical inspection according to European standards and directives with the support of H-BIM to enhance its preventive maintenance and optimise the cost of subsequent interventions.						
Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The HBIM model is intended to be used for feasibility analysis of possible options to improve user’s comfort and decrease the energy consumption budget allocation prior to any intervention. • Development of the H-BIM model • Analyse of the information obtained from the current state of the building • Ensure user-friendliness to facilitate the implementation and durability of the preventive maintenance methodology. 						
Potential Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical difficulties in integrating H-BIM with real-time monitoring. • Limited accessibility or knowledge of the Digital Twin interface by users. • Resistance to methodology from building users. • Balance between modernisation and conservation of CH buildings. • Lack of or difficulty obtaining building data. 						
Equipment	<p>The equipment will be defined according to the needs detected during the development of the INHERIT project and considering the restrictions to carry out any intervention as it is a protected building.</p> <p>However, the following equipment could be a first draft.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Equipment</th> <th>Short description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Equipment Name 1</td> <td>Interactive Displays and AR-VR Interfaces</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Equipment Name 2</td> <td>H-BIM Integration Tools</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Equipment	Short description	Equipment Name 1	Interactive Displays and AR-VR Interfaces	Equipment Name 2	H-BIM Integration Tools
Equipment	Short description						
Equipment Name 1	Interactive Displays and AR-VR Interfaces						
Equipment Name 2	H-BIM Integration Tools						

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	Equipment Name 3	Real-time Monitoring Sensors																	
Datasets	<p>The datasets will be selected according to the needs detected during the development of the INHERIT project.</p> <p>However, the following datasets could be a first draft.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Datasets</th> <th>Short description</th> <th>Size</th> <th>Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)</th> <th>Means for data collection</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Dataset Name 1</td> <td>Temporal recordings on Energy Use (when existing)</td> <td>TBD</td> <td>Private</td> <td>Technical measuring and historical records</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dataset Name 2</td> <td>Building Structural Data from H-BIM</td> <td>TBD</td> <td>Private</td> <td>3D laser scanning and/or architectural documentation.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Datasets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection	Dataset Name 1	Temporal recordings on Energy Use (when existing)	TBD	Private	Technical measuring and historical records	Dataset Name 2	Building Structural Data from H-BIM	TBD	Private	3D laser scanning and/or architectural documentation.
Datasets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection															
Dataset Name 1	Temporal recordings on Energy Use (when existing)	TBD	Private	Technical measuring and historical records															
Dataset Name 2	Building Structural Data from H-BIM	TBD	Private	3D laser scanning and/or architectural documentation.															

User Scenario ID	US [6.2]
User Scenario Title	Recommendation on Historic Urban Landscape for cost-effective and less disruptive modernisation and preservation of the CH building
Pilot	Pilot 6
Relevant Service(s)	s.0 Heritage building smartification & data exchange s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning
Description	Assessment of the impact of different renovation packages to find the optimal renovation strategies. Considering also the support from stakeholders in the decision-making process towards optimal financing. Application of Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) methods and analysis to find optimal renovation strategies.
Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the impact of different renovations in the building Assess (analysis) of the optimal renovation strategy to develop in the building according to diverse criteria (considering the energy situation, reuse and preservation of the building). Collaboration with stakeholders to make decisions towards optimal financing
Potential Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resistance to change in adopting smartification technologies. Complexity in integrating heritage building data for decision support.
Equipment	The equipment will be defined according to the needs detected during the development of the INHERIT project.

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	Equipment	Short description				
	Equipment Name 1					
Datasets	The datasets will be selected according to the needs detected during the development of the INHERIT project.					
	Datasets	Short description	Size	Data Level (Open or Private)	Diss. (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Name 1					

Pilot 7 - City of Visby, UNESCO World Heritage Site, Sweden

User Scenario ID	US [7.1]				
User Scenario Title	Modelling and simulation environment				
Pilot	Visby, Sweden, Pilot 7				
Relevant Service(s)	s.2 Modelling and simulation environment				
Description	Modelling exercises will evaluate the performance of different conventional measures in terms of their long-term energy savings, also focusing on aspects of comfort and assessing the benefits of each measure and of portfolios of measures. In addition, different building simulations of energy performance will be performed				
Needs	Data is needed for the energy modelling tools provided by the energy tools developers and INHERIT internal operators.				
Potential Barriers	Lack of relevant databases from the INHERIT building engineers or building owners				
Equipment	Equipment	Short description			
	Electricity meters	Smart meter installed			
	Natural gas meters or district heating inputs	Meter installed			
	Temperature meters	Thermometers			
	Illumination meters	Illumination gauge			
	Water meters	Meter installed			

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Datasets	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Monthly electricity bills	Bill sheet or receipt		Private	Provided by the building engineer or owner
	Monthly water bills	Bill sheet or receipt		Private	Provided by the building engineer or owner
	Temperature measurements data series	Excel data sheet		Private	On site measurements
	Illumination measurements data series	Excel data sheet		Private	On site measurements
	Monthly natural gas bills or district heating inputs	Bill sheet or receipt		Private	Provided by the building engineer or owner

User Scenario ID	US [7.2]	
User Scenario Title	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	
Pilot	Visby, Sweden, Pilot 7	
Relevant Service(s)	s.5 Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	
Description	Based on historical data, a forecast for the future energy consumption of the building is developed considering future changes in building uses and potential interventions.	
Needs	Credible energy consumption projection to be used in the integrated assessment of future potential renovation actions to be considered	
Potential Barriers	Lack of historical data sets	
Equipment	No new equipment is installed	
	Equipment	Short description
	Energy forecasting and data driven tools as described at the Grant Agreement	

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Datasets	Historical data sets on all types of energy consumption of the building				
	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Name 1				

User Scenario ID	US [7.3]				
User Scenario Title	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance				
Pilot	Visby, Sweden, Pilot 7				
Relevant Service(s)	s.9: GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance				
Description	Spatial digital mapping of the pilot sites that would lead to replicating the solutions deployed in T5.3 across INHERIT's pilots and beyond and adapt and transfer the solutions and lessons learnt from one pilot site to other pilot sites, areas.				
Needs	GIS modelling data and analysis				
Potential Barriers	Lack of spatial digital databases of the pilots				
Equipment	GIS models				
	Equipment	Short description			
	Equipment Name 1				
Datasets	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Datasets requested by GIS experts (to be defined at a later stage)				

Pilot 8 - Ahmet Pristina City Archive & Museum (APIKAM), Turkiye

User Scenario ID	US [8.1]				
User Scenario Title	Collecting data related to energy performance				
Pilot	Pilot 8				

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Relevant Service(s)	s.2 Modelling and simulation environment				
Description	The user will be able to foresee the energy consumption of the pilot building according to different conventional measures. Being able to make long-term energy planning will be useful for future renovation decisions.				
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Collect the data of consumed electricity. 2) Collect the data of natural gas for heating. 3) Collect the data of indoor air quality. 4) Suggestions for energy optimization. 				
Potential Barriers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The accuracy of the measurements since they're provided monthly. 2) The building consists of variety of functions, each having different working hours. 				
Equipment	Equipment		Short description		
	Electricity meter	Electricity meters exist on the building, measures monthly			
	Heat meter	Natural gas meters exist on the building, measures monthly			
	Water meter	Water meter exists on the building, measures monthly			
Datasets	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Electricity	Electricity bills		Private	
	Natural gas	Natural gas bills			
	Water	Water bills			

User Scenario ID	US [8.2]
User Scenario Title	Enhancement of crowd and mobility management
Pilot	Pilot 8
Relevant Service(s)	s.7 Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns
Description	The user will obtain more detailed data on crowd management, accessibility management and evacuation scenarios of the building.
Needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Gathering data on mobility patterns to host more effectively exhibitions, seminars, workshops etc. 2) Gathering data to improve IEQ (Indoor Environment Quality)

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Potential Barriers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The different uses of the building are specific; this reduces flexibility in directing users from one place to another. 2) The building provides a variety of functions, each of which has different working hours. 				
Equipment	Equipment		Short description		
	Equipment Name 1				
Datasets	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Name 1				

Annex B

s.1 Interactive screen usage and AR-VR interfaces

Service ID						
Service name s.1 Interactive screen usage and AR-VR interfaces						
Lead Partner UCL						
General Description						
General Description This service will encompass the hardware and software tools enabling H-BIM (s.8)/Digital Twins (s.6) support to:						
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) AR-based maintenance and renovation to reduce maintenance and renovation time and improve work quality, as providing the different maintenance/renovation scenarios in DT, 2) AR-based human-machine interaction to support on-the-job training, 3) VR-based pre-intervention planning by evaluating three aspects on the Spanish and Polish demo sites. There are three subtasks (3.1) optimising costs and schedules, helping detect errors at early stage before they become costly problems to achieve preventative/ predictive maintenance, (3.2) promoting engagement with stakeholders and on-site personnel, making refurbishment projects more accessible to a wider range of clients, (3.3) allowing on-site users to familiarize themselves with the site before any work begins through pre-training. <p>Motivation: The motivation is to develop an AR/VR platform and interaction user interact to support the design and renovation construction for the heritage building.</p>						
Service Functionalities						
Input Data	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. (Open or Private)	Level	Means for data collection
	Digital model 1	Pilot 5 geometric and semantic information of historical buildings	1GB	Private		using RGB camera or laser scanner to capture the geometric and semantic information
	Digital model 2	The digital model of Pilot 6. Geometric and semantic information of historical buildings	1GB	Private		using RGB camera or laser scanner to capture the geometric and semantic information
Output Data	The output is the user interface and the AR/ VR platform to support the building design and renovation. Additionally, there are many simulation results in different designs, renovation construction and maintenance scenarios.					
Service Workflow	Step 1: Data collection (RGB high-resolution images/ point cloud data) Step 2: Build the 3D/digital models of heritage buildings Step 3: Design the user interface based on Unity Step4: Develop the functions based on the needs/requirements of various renovation, maintenance and construction activities. Step 5: Develop the user interface to allow users to interact with the AR/VR platform					
Internal architecture &	Functionality: 1) visualization of heritage buildings,					

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Technologies used	<p>2) visualization of the maintenance process in different maintenance/renovation scenarios in DT,</p> <p>3) support on –the-job training.</p> <p>4) VR-based pre-intervention planning.</p> <p>5) optimising costs and schedules,</p> <p>6) promoting engagement with stakeholders and onsite personnel,</p> <p>7) allowing on-site users to familiarize themselves with the site</p> <p>Technologies: AR technology, VR technology, photogrammetry, Point cloud, BIM and digital twins.</p> <p>Tool: AR unity platform, VR device, DT software, such as Cloud Compare.</p>
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s.2 Modelling & simulation environment

Service ID					
Service name	s.2 Modelling & simulation environment				
Lead Partner	UPRC				
General Description					
General Description	<p>Based on the existing literature on historical buildings, there is an increased need to understand how to achieve energy and cost-efficient strategies in historical buildings, as well as to examine the possible impact of these measures on the environment. The aim of this service is to assess renovation strategies for the pilots 4, 7 and 8. The service will use a bottom-up simulation model to derive dynamic simulations calibrated with in-situ measurements for each building. The service will help us understand the energy-saving potential of different renovation actions in these buildings and the results will serve as input for the work done in s.3, especially for the cost-optimal assessment and the calculation of the economic parameters for the multicriteria decision framework. The outcome of this service should guide owners and facilitators of historical buildings to apply cost-effective energy efficient measures.</p>				
Service Functionalities					
Input Data		Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Building characteristics	Information about the building characteristics (e.g., size of windows, walls, heating systems, etc.)		Open	Template developed under T5.1 /Excel file if additional info is needed

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	Energy efficiency measures catalogue	Information regarding the renovation actions to be simulated		Open	Excel file
Output Data	Energy consumption of the building (baseline), energy savings achieved through the actions explored. The users will have the opportunity to see how different energy actions will impact the energy consumption of the building.				
Service Workflow	The service consists of 6 main steps: (1) data collection for the baseline of the building (2) creating the dynamic energy simulation model of the building, (3) validating the energy simulation model by using collected data, (4) data about the energy efficient actions and their feasibility in the building (5) applying energy-efficient improvement scenarios and (6) conducting a cost-optimal analysis (optional).				
Internal architecture & Technologies used	<p>The Dynamic high-resolution dEmand-side Management (DREEM) model is a hybrid bottom-up model that combines the key features of both statistical and engineering models. The model serves as an entry point in Demand-Side Management modeling in the building sector, by expanding the computational capabilities of existing Building Energy System models to assess the benefits and limitations of demand-flexibility, primarily for consumers, and for other power actors involved.</p> <p><i>GitHub link:</i> https://github.com/TEESlab-UPRC/DREEM</p>				

s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning

Service ID	
Service name	s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning
Lead Partner	UU supported by ICCS and CARTIF
General Description	
General Description	<p>The developed decision support tool for optimal renovation planning for cultural heritage buildings will be based on outranking multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) methods. This specific group of MCDA methods are best suited for group decision aiding for energy and environmental decision problems since they decompose the problem into measurable attributes and encompass a non-compensatory criteria aggregation algorithm that supports a strong sustainability concept. This means that a very poor performance of a possible alternative to one criterion cannot be fully compensated by a very good performance in another criterion. In that way critical environmental and cultural values can be preserved.</p> <p>The goal of this tool will be to develop and apply a MCDA methodological framework to improve the condition of the historical buildings through efficient decision-making for</p>

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

optimal renovation considering environmental, economic, cultural heritage and societal factors as well as stakeholders' needs.

The developed tool will be used across the following steps:

- Identification of alternative energy efficiency and other renovation measures/actions suitable for historical buildings. These may include actions that target the curbing of the heating and cooling demands; identification of the most effective retrofit measures; minimizing the energy use in the building in a cost-effective manner while satisfying the users' needs. Retrofit and energy efficiency measures which can be applied in historic buildings are much more limited due to preservation of valuable properties of the buildings.
- Establishment of sustainability evaluation criteria (energy, economy, environment, technology, societal), scales, units of measurement and way of assessment
- Selection and operationalization of MCDA method(s), for example PROMETHEE II, ELECTRE III. Partial compensation between the criteria or no compensation between the criteria could be allowed based on user's and analyst's preferences
- Stakeholders' preference elicitation and modelling
- Model application and initial results
- Feedback and analysis

Service Functionalities

		Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
Input Data	Energy balance sheet for heating: input – output analysis	Heat demand: type and amount of energy used to cover heat demand	Should cover at least one year of operation	Private	Pilot data
	Energy balance sheet for cooling: input – output analysis	Cooling demand: type and amount of energy used to cover cooling demand	Should cover at least one year of operation	Private	Pilot data
	Energy balance sheet for electrical appliances: input – output analysis	Electrical appliances demand: amount of energy used to cover electrical appliances demand	Should cover at least one year of operation	Private	Pilot data
	Energy balance sheet for hot water demand:	Hot water demand: type and amount of	Should cover at least one	Private	Pilot data

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	input – output analysis	energy used to cover hot water demand	year of operation		
	Construction material database	Building envelope, roof, floor, windows.	Example: U values of materials	Private	Pilot data from building engineers
Output Data	Heat demand assessment; cooling demand assessment; electrical appliances demand assessment; hot water demand assessment; potential renovation measures will be identified together with their environmental impact and implementation cost; data base of wider societal actors' (users, stakeholders, decision-makers, shadow players, etc.) preferences will be established via interviews, surveys, focus groups, etc. Note: A detailed presentation of the output data cannot be made now, since this will also be one of the main research elements under investigation.				
Service Workflow	The service will be a methodological framework and tool that would guide decision-makers to: identify available and plausible renovation actions; develop sustainability criteria to assess these actions together with the related scales, units of measurement and ways of assessment; evaluate the performance of each action to each criterion; elicit and model the preference of stakeholders on these criteria, rank potential actions from best to worst based on individual performance and criteria weights; initiate feedback and decision loop; propose solution(s)				
Internal architecture & Technologies used					

s.4 IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation

Service ID	
Service name	s.4 IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation
Lead Partner	ICCS
General Description	
General Description	The ultimate objective of the service is to improve the well-being of the CH building occupants, while considering the environmental conditions required for the preservation of the CH assets. In this regard, the service will involve the utilization of data-driven models that measure thermal, visual, and acoustic comfort, as well as indoor air quality, and provide recommendations for improving overall IEQ. More specifically, the models will support the evaluation of the IEQ across its different components in key areas of the buildings, the detection of anomalies and bad practices, and the proposal of changes in building occupants'

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

behaviour and building’s operational settings that balance health and safety with energy consumption. When possible, users’ feedback will also be exploited to enhance the insights provided by the service.

Service Functionalities

Input data may differ depending on the objectives of each implementation. Nevertheless, in general, the following data will be required.

	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection	
Input Data	Energy consumption for heating and cooling	The data should illustrate for each building area of interest the hours the heating/cooling system(s) operated, and the energy consumed for that purpose.	Should cover at least one year of operation	Private	Pilot data
	Variables related with IEQ	The data should illustrate for each building area of interest and at an hourly level the quantities required for computing IEQ variables (e.g. temperature, humidity, CO2 concentration, noise level).	Should cover at least one year of operation	Private	Pilot data
	Variables related to outdoor environmental conditions	The data should illustrate at an hourly level key variables related to outdoor environmental conditions that help extract insights about the factors that influence IEQ	Should cover at least one year of operation	Private	Either pilot data or third-party services

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

		(e.g. outdoor temperature, noise level).			
	Feedback of building occupants	Answers provided by building occupants about their comfort and the IEQ.	Optional	Private	Pilot data obtained through questionnaires
Output Data	<p>The output of the service may include one or more of the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Detailed measurements of IEQ components and relevant assessments. 2. List of hours and days where anomalies and bad practices have been identified. 3. Recommendations about the hours the heating/cooling system should operate to improve thermal comfort during occupancy hours. This includes pre-heating actions and proposals about the set point temperature to be used. 4. Insights based on historical analysis data about the spaces that are most suitable for working, meeting, etc. per period (e.g. time of the day or month). 5. Proposals about measures that could improve IEQ in terms of both operational and behavioural changes. 				
Service Workflow	<p>The workflow of the service is summarized as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user opens the service on the platform, getting an overview of the building (key building details). • On the first page, the user observes key IEQ variables using both historical and real-time data. In the respective graphs, the user can inspect potential anomalies and bad practices, i.e. instances where IEQ was inadequate. Moreover, the user can inspect the IEQ variables in comparison to the energy consumed. Finally, the user can inspect the feedback provided by the building occupants about IEQ, when available, and get insights about potential improvements. • On the second page, the user finds a table showing which areas of the building are most suitable for working, meeting, etc. per time-period based on the IEQ typically realized per case. By changing the time interval under investigation (hour, day, month) the insights dynamically change. • On the third page, the user finds proposals about indicative measures that could be considered for improving the IEQ of the examined areas based on their special characteristics, use, and the CH assets involved. These can include technical improvements but will mostly focus on soft measures like operational and behavioural changes. • On the last page, the user finds recommendations for the following few day(s) regarding the time the heating/cooling system should operate and the set point temperature that should be considered. The recommendation will change dynamically based on the sensor data collected, the forecasts generated for the indoor environmental conditions, and the simulations taking place. 				
Internal architecture &	<p>The service will be presented to the user through an online GUI, which can be conveniently accessed via standard web browsers. The front-end and the back-end will be interconnected</p>				

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Technologies used	<p>through APIs, with a relational database serving as the repository for managing IEQ information.</p> <p>For the front-end the technology that will probably be used is <i>Angular</i>, supplemented by various libraries.</p> <p>For the back-end, <i>.NET</i> will be used, complementing <i>Python</i> for the algorithms, and supported with other libraries, such as <i>fastAPI</i>.</p> <p>To enhance deployment and scalability, the service will be encapsulated within a Docker image, ensuring efficient and consistent deployment across diverse environments.</p>
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s.5 Energy forecasting and intelligent management

Service ID					
Service name	s.5 Energy forecasting and intelligent management				
Lead Partner	ICCS				
General Description					
General Description	<p>The ultimate objective of the service is to improve the energy management of CH buildings by providing accurate forecasts and data-driven recommendations. To achieve this goal, first, a set of forecasting models will be developed, tasked with accurately predicting the energy consumed in particular areas of the buildings or in total, the indoor environmental conditions of the building areas, or special, intensive energy uses of the building (e.g. heating, cooling, lighting etc.) that energy management could focus on. This will include state-of-the-art ML models but also novel approaches, including Transfer Learning and Domain Adaptation, among others. In terms of optimization, intelligent energy management will focus on load shifting with the objective of reducing cost, shaving peaks or exploiting the benefits that energy production from RES and energy storage can offer.</p>				
Service Functionalities					
Input Data	Input data may differ depending on the objectives of each implementation. Nevertheless, in general, the following data will be required.				
		Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Energy consumption	The data should illustrate for each building area and/or energy use of interest the energy consumed.	Should cover at least one year of operation	Private	Pilot data
Energy management constraints	Information about the limitations	N/A	Private	Energy manager	

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

		<p>present and other operational constraints that should be considered when shifting loads (e.g. hours of operation, thermal comfort)</p>
Output Data	<p>The output of the service may include one or more of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forecasts for the following hours, days or weeks, summarizing the energy that is expected to be consumed per energy use, building area or in total. • A schedule showing when flexible loads could operate based on the optimization criteria defined. 	
Service Workflow	<p>The workflow of the service is summarized as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user opens the service on the platform, getting an overview of the building (key building details). • On the first page, the user observes, in relevant graphs, the actual energy consumed by the building at different levels (e.g. in total, per area or energy use) and the forecasts provided by the models per case. A table summarizing the accuracy of the models will also be available. • On the second page, the user observes the energy consumed in the building in real-time and the forecasts generated for the following periods, serving as a basis for the optimizations. • On the last page, the user inspects a schedule, indicating when each of the shiftable loads should operate based on the optimization criteria defined. 	
Internal architecture & Technologies used	<p>The service will be exposed to the user through an online GUI, which can be conveniently accessed via standard web browsers. The front-end and the back-end will be interconnected through APIs, with a relational database serving as the repository for managing loads and forecasts.</p> <p>For the front-end the technology that will probably be used is <i>Angular</i>, supplemented by various libraries.</p> <p>For the back-end, <i>.NET</i> will be used, complementing <i>Python</i> for the algorithms, and supported with other libraries, such as <i>fastAPI</i>.</p> <p>To enhance deployment and scalability, the service will be encapsulated within a Docker image, ensuring efficient and consistent deployment across diverse environments.</p>	

s.6 Digital Twin for Heritage facilities' real time monitoring operation & management

Service ID	
Service name	s.6 Digital Twin for Heritage facilities' real time monitoring operation & management

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Lead Partner	CEMOSA
General Description	
General Description	<p>The digital twin to be developed in INHERIT is a virtual replica of the cultural heritage building and is used to provide meaningful information about the CH operation & management (energy & comfort) to building users and maintenance managers.</p> <p>The CH digital twin includes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Static data of the CH and its systems included in the BIM models. 2) Dynamic data of the CH provided by the monitoring systems. 3) Data processing provides indicators and scores of CH and users performance. 4) Energy performance models which allows simulate scenarios and carry out what-if analysis about potential conservation measures. <p>The digital twin will be a comprehensive twin (level 4) according to the levels defined by Autodesk*¹</p> <p>The DT system enables:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Remote inspection and visualization of real-time and historical energy and indoor environment quality data 2. Energy and indoor environment quality analysis and monitoring 3. Generation and visualization of energy & IEQ performance deviation alarms 4. Automatic sensors incidences detection 5. Quantifying savings potential based on an optimally operated and maintained reference CH 6. Enable simulation scenarios and what-if analysis to evaluate conservation measures with high accuracy 7. Visualize all data and calculations in the DT graphical interface which is divided into a 3D visualization (BIM based) and a navigation/control panel
Service Functionalities	
Input Data	<p>DS1- Static CH data. The DT enables the visualization of all the static data included in the BIM model of the CH. The information will be collected through the BIM model file (it can be an ifc file, a rvt file, etc.). The information that should be included in the BIM file is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General information: Location, address • Geometry: spaces distribution • Envelope materials: walls, roofs, ceilings, floors • Lighting system: location, geometry, type, power (W) • Other equipment: PCs, printers, elevators • HVAC system: production, distribution and terminal units elements and features <p>DS2- Dynamic monitoring data on CH performance. The DT collects, visualizes, and exploits real-time data on building performance. There are several means for data collection. The DT system can connect to the monitoring system or BACS in the CH building using MQTT, API, etc. The situation depends on each pilot with the data set size depending on the pilot size and monitoring level. It is recommended to collect data every 5 minutes. The data collected for the first pillar (energy and comfort) is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy consumption: monitored both at building level and room level by type of consumption (total, lighting, air conditioning, other equipment). • Outdoor environment: the system should monitor outdoor temperature, humidity, and solar radiation in the location of the CH.

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

- Indoor environment: temperature, humidity and CO2 should be measured for each room while other variables such as lighting level could be also measured depending on the pilot

DS3 – Energy and IEQ performance models to calculate scores and carry out what-if analysis. The BEM models are developed with Python & Energy plus files (.py, .idf)

	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
Dataset Name 1	BIM static data	Depending on pilot size	Pilot decision	Upload the BIM file in the DT
Dataset Name 2	Dynamic monitoring data on CH performance	Depends on pilot size and monitoring level. Variables to be collected every 5 minutes	Pilot decision	If possible, json file using mqtt, api, etc.
Dataset Name 3	BEM models	-	-	Python and energy (.py ; idf)

Output Data

- 1- Visualization of real-time and historical energy and indoor environment quality monitoring data in the BIM model and navigation panel (values & heatmap displays in the BIM model; graph displays in the navigation/control panel)
- 2- Energy and IEQ alarms displayed in the BIM models and navigation/control panel (e.g. lights were on last night in room XX, you have wasted X €)
- 3- Energy and IEQ dynamic scores displayed in the BIM model (values & heat maps) and the navigation/control panel (graphs)
- 4- Reference optimally operated and maintained CH building consumption (kWh) displayed in the navigation/control panel and compared to the real CH building (graphs)
- 5- Energy consumption savings (kWh, €, %, etc.) corresponding to a potential conservation measure or scenario displayed in the navigation/control panel (graphs)

Service Workflow

F1: Remote inspection and visualization of real-time and historical energy and indoor environment quality data	
Objective	Display monitoring data interesting for the users: energy consumption per use (HVAC, lighting, equipment), etc. and per location; temperatures or CO2 per location.
Stakeholder	building user, facility manager
Input data	Monitoring data
Output data	Monitoring data
Workflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collect monitoring data Link data to spaces Display real time data on BIM model.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Display historical data when a space is selected
Technical requirements	Real-time update of the digital twin

F2: Energy and indoor environment quality analysis and monitoring

Objective	Display energy and IEQ analysis interesting for the users
Stakeholder	Facility managers
Input data	Monitoring data
Output data	Thermal maps visualization
workflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect monitoring data • Link data to spaces • Compare data collected with target values according to regulation or energy efficiency criteria • Coloured spaces and visualized in BIM model according to energy efficiency and IEQ levels following a gradient.
Technical requirements	Calculate levels of energy efficiency and IEQ per spaces

F3: Generation and visualization of energy efficiency and IEQ deviation alarms

Objective	The objective is to identify deviations in the operation of the CH that result in poor performance or higher consumption than expected in order to inform the maintenance manager so that he/she can carry out the necessary maintenance tasks. In addition, inefficient behaviours of the users will be identified, and recommendations will be sent to correct them.
Stakeholder	Station users, facility managers
Input data	Real station KPIs, reference thresholds
Output data	Energy efficiency alarms, maintenance alarms, criticality level, performance or behaviour impact
Workflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect real station KPIs • Compare KPIs with reference thresholds • Identify deviation • Generate alarms • Visualize in DT user interface
Technical requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable end-user to easily visualize alarms • Enable end-user to manage alarms (identify, close, etc.)

F4: Quantifying potential savings based on an optimally operated and maintained reference CH.

Objective	Score the CH and user's performance, comparing the real CH with a reference CH that is a mirror of the real CH but optimally operated and maintained.
Stakeholder	Energy expert, facility manager, CH manager, CH users
Input data	BIM model, energy model, monitoring data, occupancy model, weather data
Output data	Energy scores, energy consumption for calibrated station and reference station

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Workflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic simulation and calibration of real CH • Automatic simulation and calibration of reference CH • Automatic collection of simulation results for calibrated and reference CH. • Automatic comparison of simulation results and calculate CH scores. • Graph automatically scores per energy use and location. • Graph automatically references station consumption and calibrated CH consumption per use (HVAC, lighting, equipment, etc.) and location.
Technical requirements	Interoperability between BIM, energy calculation and monitoring data

F5: Enable simulation scenarios and what-if analysis. Evaluation of energy saving measures with high accuracy

Objective	Evaluation and comparison of different Energy Conservation Measures (ECM)
Stakeholder	Energy experts, CH manager/owner, facility manager
Input data	CH energy model, Monitoring data, ECM energy model
Output data	Energy simulation outputs and comparison
Workflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulate and calibrate real CH model • Simulate energy conservation measures • Compare and visualize energy saving, costs, etc. for every energy conservation measure
Technical requirements	Interoperability between BIM, energy calculation and monitoring data

F6: Digital Twin visualization

Objective	Visualizations in the DT user interface: BIM model, monitoring data, KPIs, energy scores, alarms and energy conservation measures
Stakeholder	CH users, facility manager, station owner/manager
Input data	BIM model, monitoring data, data processing results, simulation results
Output data	Digital Twin visualization
workflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect monitoring data from DT database. • Collect BIM model from DT database. • Collect KPIs and energy scores from DT database. • Collect alarms from DT database • Collect ECM simulation results from DT database • Link all data with the BIM model • Display information in the DT interface: panel and 3D model
Technical requirements	

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Internal architecture & Technologies used

MQTT is an option, we can also use an api or other alternatives to collect monitoring data. We can also connect to the data space to collect and exploit dynamic data.

s.7 Real-time insights on activity and mobility partners

Service ID					
Service name	s.7 Real-time insights on activity and mobility partners				
Lead Partner	SLG				
General Description					
General Description	The service provides pilot administrators and staff with real-time data and analytics regarding visitor activity and mobility within the premises. By leveraging advanced tracking technologies and data analytics, this service offers valuable real-time insights into visitors' behaviour, crowd flow patterns, and more. This information helps management optimize visitor experiences, allocate resources efficiently, and make data-driven decisions to enhance overall operations.				
Service Functionalities					
Input Data	Input data may differ depending on the objectives of each implementation. Nevertheless, in general, the following data will be required.				
		Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Past visitation patterns	This data illustrates the historical data of visits, and crown allocation within the pilot	Should cover at least one year of operation	Private	Pilot data
	Any existing monitoring footage from the pilots	Any data recorded by the pilots' employees, by either already existing equipment or any other means	Should cover at least one year of operation	Private	Pilot data

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

Output Data	<p>The output of the service may include one or more of the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Real-time alerts. 2. Traffic flow analysis. 3. Visitor engagement metrics. 4. Heatmaps
Service Workflow	<p>The workflow of the service is summarized as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Collection: Sensors placed strategically throughout the pilots' collect data on visitor movement, and other relevant parameters. • Data Processing: The collected data is transmitted to a centralized system where it undergoes preprocessing and analysis. Advanced algorithms are applied to extract meaningful insights and identify patterns in visitor behaviour. • Insights Generation: The analysed data is used to generate actionable insights and visualizations, such as visitor heatmaps, exhibit engagement metrics, and traffic flow analyses. • Decision Support: Pilot administrators and staff utilize the generated insights to make informed decisions regarding exhibit placement, signage optimization, staff deployment, and other operational aspects. • Continuous Monitoring: The system operates in real time, continuously monitoring visitor activity and mobility patterns within the pilot premises. Any significant deviations or anomalies trigger real-time alerts for immediate attention and action by pilot staff.
Internal architecture & Technologies used	<p>The service will employ open-source image processing software, such as OpenCV, and machine learning algorithms like YOLO (You Only Look Once), leveraging these technologies as black boxes to derive results.</p>

s.8 Preventive maintenance with H-BIM

Service ID	
Service name	s.8 Preventive maintenance with H-BIM
Lead Partner	CARTIF
General Description	
General Description	<p>The H-BIM tool, developed as a fundamental part of this service, aims to improve the management and conservation of heritage buildings through multidimensional modelling. The goal of this service is to integrate data derived from technical inspections into a collaborative H-BIM model with a referenced information structure, enabling a global analysis of interventions in historic buildings and improving their maintenance costs and sustainability. Designed specifically for the INHERIT project, the tool complies with European standards, including BIM level 2 and energy performance improvement (EN 16883:2017). It ensures interoperability using non-proprietary formats such as IFC.</p>
Service Functionalities	

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

		Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
Input Data	Data on the current conditions of the building	Data derived from the current status of the building, covering information on foundations, structure, façades, roofs, installations, biodegradation, watertightness, beauty, accessibility and functional performance. These data are collected using the technical inspection methodology developed in WP3.	TBD	Private	Pilot data provision
	Buildings data from Cadastral data	Data should include year of construction of all buildings, buildings' geometry (boundary and area), buildings' height, buildings' use and/or typology.	TBD	Private	Pilot data provision
	Historical data on building interventions	The data should include technical information on any refurbishment, restoration, and renovation that has been carried out on the building during its lifetime.	TBD	Private/Open	Pilot data provision/ Open Data (Regional government publications)
	Data on the heritage value of the building and its construction phases	The data should be useful for interpreting the rest of the data on the building and its social and cultural context.	TBD	Private/Open	Pilot data provision/Open Data
Output Data	The output of the service is a collaborative H-BIM model structured with a multi-layered information system. This model will allow the multidimensional analysis of interventions in historic buildings, addressing aspects that can range from the 4D (evolution) to the 7D (maintenance) BIM dimension to improve the energy performance of historic buildings and their maintenance costs.				
Service Workflow	<p>Describe a sequence of steps to explain the internal logic of the service:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the service on a BIM platform. 2. The 3D model of the historic building appears, which can be manipulated by the user in a collaborative way. 3. The user can select elements of the model and consult the information associated with it. 4. The user can add new information to the model and update the data periodically/dynamically. 				

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	<p>5. The user can obtain tables with data to make a global analysis of the current state of the model and simulate maintenance actions to make efficient and sustainable decisions.</p> <p>The service requires skills in BIM / H-BIM.</p>
Internal architecture & Technologies used	<p>This service does not include the development of any software application. The H-BIM model will be developed using BIM modelling software, such as Autodesk Revit or similar, complying with the European directive 2014/24/EU for BIM level 2 and ensuring interoperability through the use of non-proprietary Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) formats.</p>

s.9 GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance

Service ID					
Service name	s.9 GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance				
Lead Partner	ICCS				
General Description					
General Description	<p>The ultimate objective of the service is to guide heritage managers, engineers, architects, and building operators to identify proper maintenance plans for CH buildings based on their characteristics and similarities. To achieve this goal, the service will provide a GIS-based interface that visualizes CH buildings in an interactive map and summarizes key information about the architectural style and design of the building, its overall condition, and the CH assets involved. Moreover, by exploiting advanced image processing models, the service will cluster CH buildings into categories based on their similarity.</p>				
Service Functionalities					
Input Data		Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Building characteristics	Key, static information about the CH buildings to be analysed, including their position, ownership, architecture style, design, and year of construction.	TBD	Open	Gathered from third party sources in collaboration with the pilot.
	Building images	Images of CH buildings within	TBD	Open	Gathered from third

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

		the broader area of the pilot that can help analyse their design, condition, and particularities.		party sources in collaboration with the pilot.
Output Data	<p>The output of the service may include the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. An interactive map, presenting the CH buildings within the examined area. The user will be able to inspect the buildings by reviewing key information related to their style, design, and image. 2. A list, showing the constructed classes and the buildings included in each category, along with features that contributed most to said categorization. 			
Service Workflow	<p>The workflow of the service is summarised as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user opens the service on the platform and accesses a map where the broader area of the pilot is presented, and the CH buildings are displayed. By clicking on the buildings, the user can obtain information about their special characteristics. • On another page, the user can observe the clusters constructed and the features that contributed most to their categorizations. This includes summary statistics about the examined buildings, both static and graphical. 			
Internal architecture & Technologies used	<p>The service will be presented to the user through an online GUI, which can be conveniently accessed via standard web browsers. The front-end and the back-end will be interconnected through APIs, with a database serving as the repository for handling GIS-related data and images.</p> <p>For the front-end, the technology that will probably be used is <i>Angular</i>, supplemented by various libraries.</p> <p>For the back-end, <i>.NET</i> will be used, complementing <i>Python</i> for the algorithms, and supported with other libraries, such as <i>fastAPI</i>. Special technologies (TBD) will be used for integrating the GIS system and maps with the service.</p> <p>To enhance deployment and scalability, the service will be encapsulated within a Docker image, ensuring efficient and consistent deployment across diverse environments.</p>			

s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios

Service ID	
Service name	s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios
Lead Partner	CARTIF
General Description	
General Description	The service calculates the risk of climate change on building stock based on the generation of simplified assessment models at a city level covering the exposure, vulnerability and probability of occurrence of hazardous events. The evolution of the energy demand according to different hazard scenarios will be calculated and integrated with socio-

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

economic variables to assess the building stock vulnerability and, at the end, the Expected Annual Losses (EAL) associated with each hazard scenario. These hazard scenarios will be developed using CMIP6 scenario data (SSPs-RCs) from Copernicus CS3 and a downscaling procedure join a bias-correction with historical data from weather stations. This will allow for the analyse of the effects of different risks under each climate scenario on the building stock, providing an understanding of how it will be affected in the future by climate change. In the end, the most relevant risks affecting CH buildings according to the most prominent climate hazards will be assessed, calculating relevant KPIs to compare effects between climate scenarios.

Service Functionalities

		Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
Input Data	Buildings data from Cadastral data	Data should include year of construction of all buildings, buildings' geometry (boundary and area), buildings' height, buildings' use and/or typology, building characteristics (if possible), such as thermal characteristics of the envelope, window-to-wall ratio, or building materials.	TBD	Private	Pilot data provision
	OpenStreetMap	Map data to complement buildings' data from cadastral data.	TBD	Open	Open data
	DTM and DSM, or LiDAR data instead	DTM (Digital Terrain Model) and DSM (Digital Surface Model), in case no height is available in cadastral data.	TBD		Pilot data provision
	Historical data from weather stations	Temperature data for at least 30 years	TBD	Private	Pilot data provision
	Weather data from PVGIS	Weather data including solar radiation data	TBD	Open	Open data
	Solar data from GlobalSolarAtlas		TBD	Open	Open data

D2.3 Consolidation factors for the INHERIT decision support services

	Copernicus C3S	Future climate data from different climate change scenarios	TBD	Open	Open data
Output Data	<p>The output of the service is a map visualization of the building stock of the pilot area (city level) using a coloured scale to present the results of the calculation of the relevant risks affecting CH buildings according to the most prominent climate hazards (through different climate scenarios). Relevant KPIs to compare the effects of the hazards between climate scenarios will be calculated.</p> <p>Also, as the map is interactive, the user will be able to click on each building to see its complete information, both the information previously available and the information calculated by the service.</p>				
Service Workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the service on the Platform 2. A coloured map appears showing the building stock's climate change risk, through the exposure, vulnerability and probability of occurrence of hazardous events in the whole city (pilot area). 3. The energy demand of the building stock can also be visualised to understand its evolution according to the climate scenarios. 4. The Expected Annual Losses for each hazard scenario are visualised, according to the different CMIP6 climate scenarios (SSPs-RCPs). 5. The user can move around the map and can zoom into an area to see some parts in more detail. 6. The user can click into a specific building to see further information on it (e.g. all available information: construction year, typology, building characteristics, the Expected Annual Losses, etc.) 7. In a menu, the user can change the hazard scenario to see the projection for the building stock. 				
Internal architecture & Technologies used	<p>The Service will be exposed to the user through an online Graphical User Interface, which can be conveniently accessed via standard web browsers. The front-end and the back-end will be interconnected through APIs, with a PostGIS database serving as the repository for managing geolocated information.</p> <p>For the front-end, the technologies that probably will be used are <i>Angular</i>, supplemented by various libraries such as <i>leaflet</i> (for maps) or <i>Plotly</i> and <i>ECharts</i> (for graphical representations).</p> <p>For the back-end, <i>.NET</i> will be used, complementing with <i>Python</i> for the algorithms, and supported with other libraries as <i>fastAPI</i>.</p> <p>To enhance deployment and scalability, the service will be encapsulated within a Docker image, ensuring efficient and consistent deployment across diverse environments.</p>				